

Recognition and Enforcement of Arbitral Awards in Tanzania: An Appraisal of the Law, Procedure and Practice

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Abstract:

Since arbitration is a consent-based dispute resolution mechanism, parties consensually agree in an arbitration clause to resort to arbitration and to be bound by the decision of the arbitral tribunal they have consensually appointed to arbitrate their dispute. This view implies that, once an arbitral award is rendered by the arbitral tribunal, an award-debtor should immediately honour it in order to signify that party's sincere respect for the sacrosanct autonomy to consensually agree to go to arbitration. However, where the award-debtor does not voluntarily and immediately honour the arbitral award, the award-creditor is at liberty to commence recognition and enforcement proceedings in the court of competent jurisdiction. As this article contends, both under the repealed and the current arbitration legal regimes in Mainland Tanzania, there have been uncertainties as to what is the proper procedure for filing in court arbitral awards for recognition and enforcement. However, the article highlights that the current arbitration legislation, practice and caselaw have rectified this anomaly and now the procedure is clearly spelt out in the following sequence: a party should file the arbitral award in court for registration, the court should issue notice to the parties to show course why the award should not be recognised and subsequently enforced, and when the parties appear in court: (i) when they do not contest, the award should be recognised and enforced as a decree of the court, and (ii) where a party wants to challenge the award, such party will have to file a petition for challenging the same and the court would stay the proceedings for recognition and enforcement of the award pending the outcome of the petition for challenging the award. The article further notes that applications for recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards must be filed within the timeframe set out in the relevant law, otherwise the court will dismiss such application for being time-barred. Nevertheless, the article examines exceptional circumstances where an application for recognition and enforcement of an arbitral award may be entertained and granted by the court but only in its judicial discretion. Therefore, the article urges award-creditors to be mindful of both the prerequisite procedure and time-frame for filing applications for recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards, lest the same would be held incompetent and thereby prejudicing their right to realize the fruits of their respective arbitral awards.

Keywords: Arbitral Agreement, Express Consent to Arbitrate, Recognition and Enforcement of Arbitral Awards,

1. INTRODUCTION

Universally, arbitration is a consent-based dispute resolution process.¹ It is undertaken at the parties' instance as they expressly indicate their consent to arbitrate in an arbitration agreement or clause.² For that matter, consent to arbitration has always been a prerequisite to arbitration under international treaties and state legislation.³ As it was held in *Volt v. Leland*,⁴ under the law, arbitration 'is a matter of consent, not coercion, and parties are generally free to structure their arbitration agreements as they see fit.' It is universally accepted that arbitration is consensual because parties to a contract are free to agree and choose it as a method of settlement of disputes arising out of or in connection with a contract to which they are parties.⁵ Parties are also free to choose the law governing the contract and the mode of dispute settlement, including arbitration⁶ as well as that the arbitral award ensued therefrom would bind them.

It should be noted from the outset that, for arbitration to take place, parties must agree in an arbitration agreement or an investment treaty to submit disputes arising out of or in connection with the contract in question to arbitration.⁷ Therefore, it is important to note that where parties agree to insert an arbitration agreement or clause in a commercial contract or an investment treaty, such clause must be drafted in such a way that it will expressly contain the parties' consensual agreement to arbitrate. This

¹ On consent in international arbitration see particularly Steingruber, A.M., "The Mutable and Evolving Concept of 'Consent' in International Arbitration – Comparing Rules, Laws, Treaties and Types of Arbitration for a Better Understanding of the Concept of 'Consent'," *Oxford University Comparative Law Forum*, Vol. 2 (2012), available at ouclf.law.ox.ac.uk (accessed 26 February 2025); Diallo, O., *Le consentement des parties à l'arbitrage international* (PUF, 2010); Youssef, K., *Consent in Context: Fulfilling the Promise of International Arbitration, Multiparty, Multi-Contract, and Non-Contract Arbitration* (Thomson Reuters, 2011); and Steingruber, A.M., *Consent in International Arbitration* (OUP, 2012).

² In a Nigerian case of *C.N. Onuselogu Enterprises Ltd v. Afribank (Nig) Plc* (2005) 1 NWLR Part 940 page 577 (*Onuselogu v. Afribank*'), it was held that:

'[...] arbitral proceedings are recognized means of resolving disputes. [For arbitration to take place] there must be an agreement to arbitrate which is a voluntary submission to arbitration, therefore, arbitral proceedings should not be taken lightly by both counsel and the parties. They are recognized means of resolving disputes. Arbitration is said to be conventional process; a party cannot be forced to arbitrate a dispute unless he agrees to it. It is generally perceived that by any agreement containing an arbitration clause it is an indication that the contract requires the parties to resolve their disputes through an arbitration process.'

³ Okoye, A., "When Can a Non-signatory Third-party be Bound by an Arbitration Award?"; an electronic article available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4059343> (accessed 2 March 2025).

⁴ *Volt Information Sciences v. Leland Stanford, Jr. University* [1989] 489 U.S. 468 (*Volt v. Leland*).

⁵ See, for example, *Luganuzza Investment Company Ltd. v. The Trustee of Orthodox Church of Tanzania Holy Archdiocese of Mwanza*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Commercial Cause No. 49/2020 (Unreported) (*Luganuzza v. Orthodox Church*); and *Sunshine Furniture Co. Ltd. v. Maersk (China) Shipping Co. Ltd. & Nyota Tanzania Ltd.*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Civil Appeal No. 98 of 2016 (Unreported) (*Sunshine Furniture v. Maersk*).

⁶ See particularly *Louis Dreyfus Commodities Tanzania Ltd. v. Roko Investment Tanzania Ltd.* [2017] TLS LR 588 (CAT) (*Louis Dreyfus v. Roko Investment*).

⁷ *Ibid.* See also *M/S Marine Services Co. Ltd. v. M/S Gas Entec Company Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) Consolidated Misc. Commercial Causes Nos. 25 & 11/2021 (Unreported) (*Marine Services v. Gas Entec*); and *Fiona Trust & Holding Corp v. Privalov* [2007] UKHL 40 (17 October 2007) (*Fiona v. Privalov*).

presupposes that parties must incorporate into the arbitration clause all the essential ingredients, failure to do which makes the clause defective or pathological.⁸

Universally, the fundamental ingredients of an arbitration agreement include pre-arbitral procedures (such as negotiation, mediation, facilitation, expert evaluation, and adjudication); specific disputes to be referred to arbitration; number of arbitrators and the manner/procedure of their appointment; the seat of arbitration; law governing the arbitration (*lex arbitri*); time limit within which arbitrators should render their arbitral award; finality, bindingness and enforceability of the ensuing arbitral award;⁹ procedure to be followed by the arbitrator, *etc.* It should be noted, however, that these essential ingredients may differ depending on the nature or type of the envisaged arbitration.¹⁰ In totality, these ingredients of a properly drafted arbitration agreement make it an expressly agreed clause binding on the parties thereto.

It has been held that; although there is no particular form that ‘can be laid down as universal for framing an arbitration agreement’, words used for the purpose ‘must be words of choice and determination to go to arbitration and not problematic words of mere possibility.’¹¹ As such, a carefully and appropriately drafted arbitration clause normally yields into a smooth, expedient, and cost-serving dispute resolution process. In addition, an arbitration clause must expressly indicate the parties’ intention to arbitrate and to be bound by the arbitral award that would be rendered at the end of the arbitral proceedings. This entails, therefore, that a non-signatory, third-party to an arbitration agreement or clause, cannot be compelled to arbitrate, nor a non-signatory third-party cannot compel a signatory party to arbitrate. It is only in exceptional cases where an arbitration agreement may be implied or extended to a contract that has no arbitration clause. It is also only in exceptional cases where a non-signatory party can be bound by an arbitration agreement. It should be noted that case law has universally established the following exceptional instances where a non-signatory may be bound by an arbitration award:

⁸ The term “pathological clauses” (in French: or “*clauses pathologiques*”) was coined, for the first time, by the Frenchman, Frédéric Eisemann, in 1974. According to him, this term denotes arbitration agreements, and particularly arbitration clauses, which contain a defect or defects are liable to disrupt the smooth progress of the arbitration. As such, the term “pathological clauses” is widely used to describe an ambiguously drafted arbitration agreement or one laden with apparent defect(s) liable to disrupt the smooth progress of the arbitration. Such clauses may be a source of strife for the whole duration of the dispute – from jurisdictional battles to challenges at the enforcement stage. See Eisemann, F., “La clause d’arbitrage pathologique,” in *Commercial Arbitration- Essays in Memoriam Eugenio Minoli* (Torino: Unione Tipografico-editrice Torinese, 1974), p. 129. See also Davis, B., “Pathological Clauses: Frederic Eisemann’s Still Vital Criteria,” *Arbitration International*, Vol. 7, Issue 4, 1 December 1991, p. 365; and Molfa, M., “Pathological Arbitration Clauses and the Conflict of Laws,” *Hong Kong Law Journal*, Vol. 37, 2007, pp. 161-184.

⁹ See, for example, *TANESCO v. Dowans Holdings SA (Costa Rica) & Another*, High Court of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Civil Application No. 8/2011 (Unreported) (*TANESCO v. Dowans*’).

¹⁰ Srinivasan, B., “Defective Arbitration Clauses: An Overview,” *Indian Institute of Quantity Surveyors Annual Insight*, 2015, pp. 52-53.

¹¹ *Jyoti Brothers v. Shree Durga Mining Co.*, AIR 1956 Calcutta 280 (*Jyoti v. Shree Durga*’).

assignment,¹² agency relationship,¹³ incorporation by reference,¹⁴ equitable estoppel,¹⁵ piercing the incorporation veil or *alter ego*,¹⁶ and ratification or assumption.¹⁷

The rationale for the foregoing position of the law is premised on a standard arbitration principle that; since arbitration is a creation of consent,¹⁸ it is only parties that have expressly consented by an agreement (whether domestic or international) to arbitrate that reserve the right to compel or be compelled to arbitrate.¹⁹ As such, when an arbitral award is rendered the award-debtor is required to *voluntarily* honour the award as soon as it is rendered.²⁰ Where the award-debtor fails to voluntarily honour the award, the award-creditor is entitled to approach a court of competent jurisdiction to assist it in the execution of the award in terms of Sections 65 and 73 of the Arbitration Act (2020).²¹ Therefore, this article, examines the law and practice relating to enforcement of both domestic and foreign arbitral awards in Tanzania. It begins by first conceptualizing an arbitration agreement and then proceeds to examine the purpose and scope of an arbitration agreement and the essential ingredients of an arbitration agreement.

The article also makes an overview on the recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards in Tanzania. In particular, the article considers the existing two types of recognition and enforcement arbitral awards inherent in Tanzania – *i.e.*, enforcement of arbitral awards arising from court-ordered and out-of-court arbitral proceedings. In respect of the enforcement of arbitral awards arising from court-ordered arbitral proceedings, the article examines the law, procedure and practice thereof and circumstances where such awards may be remitted back to the arbitrator for reconsideration.

In respect of the recognition and enforcement of domestic and foreign arbitral awards made in out-of-court arbitral proceedings, the article examines the procedural

¹² *I & M Bank (T) Ltd. v. Bayview Properties Ltd. & Another* (Misc. Commercial Application 36 of 2022) [2022] TZHCCOMD 299 (22 September 2022) (*I&M Bank v. Bayview Properties*).

¹³ See particularly *Altobelli v. Hartmann*, 137 S. Ct. 580, 196 L. Ed. 2d 447 (2016) (*Altobelli v. Hartmann*); and *Interocean Shipping Co. v. National Shipping and Trading Corp.*, 523 F.2d 527, 539 (2d Cir. 1975) (*Interocean Shipping Co. v. National Shipping*).

¹⁴ See especially *J.S. & H Const. Co. v. Richmond County Hospital Authority*, 473 F.2d 212 (5th Cir., 1973) (*J.S. & H v. Richmond*); and *Exch. Mut. Ins. Co. v. Haskell Co.*, 742 F.2d 274 (6th Cir. 1984) (*EMIC v. Haskell*).

¹⁵ See generally *E.A.S.T., Inc. v. M/V Alaia*, 673 F. Supp. 796, 800 (E.D. La. 1987); *aff'd*, 876 F.2d 1168, (5th Cir. 1989) (*E.A.S.T., Inc. v. Alaia*); *G.E. Energy Power Conversion France S.A.S. v. Outokumpu Stainless U.S.A., L.L.C.*, 590 U.S. 2020 (*G.E. Energy Power v. Outokumpu Stainless*); and *Belzberg v. Verus Invs. Holdings Inc.*, 21 N.Y.3d 626, 999 N.E.2d 1130 (2013) (*Belzberg v. Verus*).

¹⁶ See, for example, *Cyprus Ltd. v. Adam Backstrom & Others*, 967 F Supp 1391 (Dist Conn 1997) (*Cyprus v. Adam Backstrom*); *JJ. Ryan & Sons v. Rhone Poulenc Textile, SA*, 863 F.2d 315, 320-21 (4th Cir., 1988) (*JJ. Ryan v. Rhone Poulenc*); and *Swift & Co. Packers v. Compania Colombiana Del Caribe, S.A.* 30339 U.S. 684, 1950 AMC 1089 (1950) (*Swift v. Compania Colombiana*).

¹⁷ See particularly *B.S. Sun Shipping Monrovia v. Citgo Petroleum Corp.*, 509 F. Supp. 2d 334, 347 (S.D.N.Y. 2007) (*B.S. v. Citgo Petroleum*); *Wetzel v. Sullivan, King & Sabom, P.C.*, 745 S.W.2d 78, 81-82 (Tex. App. 1988) (*Wetzel v. Sullivan*); *Caribbean SS. Co., SA v. Sonmez Denizcilik Ve Ticaret AS*, F.2d 1264 (2d Cir., 1979) (*Caribbean SS. v. Sonmez*); and *Gvozdenovic v. United Air Lines*, 933 F.2d 1100, 1103 (2d Cir. 1991) (*Gvozdenovic v. UAL*).

¹⁸ *Treasury Registrar v. A.C. Gomez (1997) Ltd.*, Commercial Application No. 71/2018: High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) (Unreported) (*TR v. Gomez*).

¹⁹ Okoye, *op. cit.*

²⁰ *Ketankumar Vinubhai Patel (Sole Arbitrator) v. Ramanlal Motibhai Patel*, Misc. Civil Cause No. 444 of 2020: High Court of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam (Unreported) (*Patel v. Patel*).

²¹ Arbitration Act (Cap. 15 2023).

steps in the recognition and enforcement of such awards and the court's discretion to refuse registering and enforcing an arbitral award. Moreover, the article canvasses the timeframe for filing in court applications for recognition and enforcing arbitral awards in Mainland Tanzania. In this regard, the article notes from the existing caselaw that there are several types of arbitral awards under different laws and 'each with its own distinct procedures for enforcement' and the timeframe for doing so.²²

The article also examines the legal consequence of delay in filing an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement as well as the exceptional circumstances in which the court may extend the time within which a party may apply for recognition and enforcement an arbitral award out of time. To conclude, the article urges award-creditors to be mindful of both the prerequisite procedure as well as the time-frame for filing applications for recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards, lest the same would be held incompetent and thereby prejudicing their right to realize the fruits of their respective arbitral awards.

2. THE CONCEPT OF ARBITRATION AGREEMENT

Often referred to as the 'foundation' of commercial arbitration,²³ an arbitration agreement or clause is, universally speaking, a clause containing the parties' agreement to use arbitration as a method of dispute resolution based on mutual consent by the parties to a contract or investment agreement to arbitrate future or current disputes.²⁴ Legally defined, an arbitration clause is 'an agreement by the parties to submit to arbitration all or certain disputes which have arisen or which may arise between them in respect of a defined legal relationship, whether contractual or not.'²⁵ Case law and the practice of drafting of arbitration clauses indicate that the envisaged disputes to be referred to arbitration may be those 'arising under' or 'arising out of' or 'in connection with' the contract in which such an arbitration clause is contained.²⁶

²² *Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Secondary School*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Application No. 40 of 2021 (Unreported) ('*Lukumbulu v. St. Anthony Sec. School*').

²³ *Tanganyika Wattle v. Dolphin Bay Chemicals*, op. cit.

²⁴ LexisNexis, "Practice Notes: Arbitration Agreements—Definition, Purpose and Interpretation," available at <https://www.lexisnexis.co.uk/legal/experts/practice-areas/arbitration> (accessed 10 February 2023).

²⁵ See particularly Section 3 of the Kenya Arbitration Act (Cap. 49 Revised Edition 2012); Section 2(1)(c) of the Uganda Arbitration and Conciliation Act (Cap. 4 of 2000); Section 3 of the Tanzania Arbitration Act (Cap. 15 R.E. 2020); and Section 7 of the India Arbitration and Conciliation Act (1996). See also Kumar, D., "Essential Ingredients of an Arbitration Agreement," April 11, 2016; available at <https://vakilsearch.com/advice/essential-ingredients-of-an-arbitration-agreement/> (accessed 11 February 2025).

²⁶ *Tanganyika Wattle v. Dolphin Bay Chemicals*, op. cit. Whereas in *Heyman v. Darwins Ltd.* [1942] AC 356, 399, Lord Porter said that the former had a narrower meaning than the latter; in *Union of India v. E.B. Aaby's Rederi A/S* [1975] AC 797, Viscount Dhorne (at p. 814) and Lord Salmon (at p. 817) held that they could not see the difference between these terms. However, in *Overseas Union Insurance Ltd. v. AA Mutual International Insurance Co. Ltd.* [1988] 2 Lloyd's Rep 63, 67, Evans J said that there was a broad distinction between clauses which referred "only those disputes which may arise regarding the rights and obligations which are created by the contract itself" and those which "show an intention to refer some wider class or classes of disputes." In *Premium Nafta Products Ltd. & Others v. Fili Shipping Ltd. & Others* [2007] EWCA Civ 20, the House of Lords held that the former 'may be said to arise "under" the contract while the latter would arise "in relation to" or "in connection with" the contract.' (per Lord Hoffmann, at para. 11). In *Fillite (Runcorn) Ltd. v. Aqua-Lift* (1989) 26 Con LR 66, 76, Slade LJ and Nourse LJ held that the phrase "under a contract" was not wide enough to include disputes which did not concern obligations created by or incorporated in the contract.

In the main, an arbitration agreement encompasses an agreement by two or more parties to submit to arbitration²⁷ either: (i) ‘future’ disputes that may arise where the agreement is set out in the substantive arbitration agreement between the parties (*i.e.*, in an arbitration clause), or (ii) ‘current’ disputes where the agreement to arbitrate is set out in a stand-alone agreement entered into between the parties after the dispute has arisen.²⁸

A leading authority that has broadly described an arbitration agreement is *Fiona v. Privalov*,²⁹ where the English House of Lords (now the UK Supreme Court) held that:

Arbitration is consensual. It depends upon the intention of the parties as expressed in their agreement. Only the agreement can tell you what kind of disputes they intended to submit to arbitration. But the meaning which parties intended to express by the words which they used will be affected by the commercial background and the reader’s understanding of the purpose for which the agreement was made. Businessmen in particular are assumed to have entered into agreements to achieve some rational commercial purpose and an understanding of this purpose will influence the way in which one interprets their language.³⁰

As such, the House of Lords held that the construction of an arbitration clause ‘should start from the assumption that the parties, as rational businessmen, are likely to have intended any dispute arising out of the relationship into which they have entered or purported to enter to be decided by the same tribunal.’³¹ According to the House of Lords, the arbitration clause should be construed ‘in accordance with this presumption unless the language makes it clear that certain questions were intended to be excluded from the arbitrator’s jurisdiction.’³² Otherwise, ‘if any businessman did want to exclude disputes about the validity of a contract, it would be comparatively easy to say so.’³³

²⁷ Idornigie, P.O., “The Implication of Poorly Drafted Arbitration Clause in a Contract,” a paper presented at the capacity building session for the Directorate of Legal Services of the National Assembly on Bill Drafting and Dispute Resolution, held in Abuja, Nigeria, on 29-31 March 2021; available at <https://paulidornigie.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/The-Implication-of-Poorly-Drafted-Arbitration-Clause-in-a-Contract-Final.1.pdf> (accessed 21 February 2025).

²⁸ According to Section 6(1) of the English Arbitration Act (Cap. 23, 1996), an “arbitration agreement” means ‘an agreement to submit to arbitration present or future disputes (whether they are contractual or not).’

²⁹ *Fiona Trust & Holding Corp v. Privalov* [2007] UKHL 40 (*Fiona v. Privalov*).

³⁰ *Ibid*, para. 5.

³¹ *Ibid*, para. 13.

³² *Ibid*.

³³ *Ibid*, para. 17 (*per* Longmore LJ).

2.1 The purpose and scope of an arbitration agreement

As it was held in *Euromec v. Shandong*,³⁴ the principal purpose of an arbitration clause is to provide ‘a specialized tribunal to hear the dispute falling within the ambit of the matters governed by the agreement.’³⁵ In *Tanganyika Wattle v. Dolphin Bay*,³⁶ the court held that:

It is trite in law that the jurisdiction of the arbitrator emanates from the arbitration agreement also known as an agreement to arbitrate. In the absence of an arbitration agreement, an arbitrator being a private person, cannot assume powers to make binding decisions upon other persons.³⁷

Elaborating on the purpose of an arbitration agreement or clause, in *Fiona v. Privalov*, the English House of Lords was of the view that:

The parties have entered into a relationship, an agreement or what is alleged to be an agreement or what appears on its face to be an agreement, which may give rise to disputes. They want those disputes decided by a tribunal which they have chosen, commonly on the grounds of such matters as its neutrality, expertise and privacy, the availability of legal services at the seat of the arbitration and the unobtrusive efficiency of its supervisory law. Particularly in the case of international contracts, they want a quick and efficient adjudication and do not want to take the risks of delay and, in too many cases, partiality, in proceedings before a national jurisdiction.³⁸

In terms of scope, the arbitration agreement is governed by several underlying principles: foremost, is the doctrine of party freedom and autonomy, which posits that parties to a contract are *free* to agree and decide *on a forum*³⁹ and *choice of law* for the determination of contractual disputes.⁴⁰ In addition, parties are *free to agree* on how their disputes should be resolved. In this regard, subject only to such safeguards as are necessary in the

³⁴ *Euromec International Ltd. v. Shandong Taikai Power Engineering Co. Ltd.* (Civil Case E527 of 2020) [2021] KEHC 93 (KLR) (Commercial and Tax) (21 September 2021) (Ruling) (*Euromec v. Shandong*).

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ *Tanganyika Wattle Co. Ltd. v. Dolphin Bay Chemicals (Pty) Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Cause No. 104 of 2023 (Arising from Misc. Commercial Cause No. 17 of 2019) (Unreported) (*Tanganyika Wattle v. Dolphin Bay*).

³⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 21. See also *Cereals and Other Produce Board of Tanzania v. Monaban Trading & Farming Co. Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Cause No. 9 of 2022 (Unreported) (*COPBT v. Monaban*).

³⁸ I *Euromec v. Shandong Taikai*, *op. cit.*, para. 6.

³⁹ *Sunshine Furniture v. Maersk*, *op. cit.*

⁴⁰ *Luganuzza v. Orthodox Church*, *op. cit.*

public interest or as provided by law;⁴¹ the court is excluded from resolving a dispute where the parties have consensually agreed to arbitrate.⁴²

Because of the doctrine of party autonomy underlying an arbitration agreement, such agreement is held to be sacrosanct and, therefore, final, binding and enforceable. Under the doctrine of sanctity of the contract, the terms and conditions set out in the arbitration clause contained in a contract which parties duly execute are to be interpreted to give effect of what the parties agreed.⁴³ As the court held in *Shamji v. TR*,⁴⁴ the doctrine of the sanctity of the arbitration agreement requires that where parties have agreed to resolve their dispute through an arbitrator, they should do so⁴⁵ instead of going to court, in which case the duty of the court is to refer them to arbitration.⁴⁶ As such, where there is in existence an agreement between the parties to refer a dispute to arbitration regardless of the nature of the complaint, the parties should go before the arbitral tribunal and not the court.⁴⁷ Therefore, as case law posits, under the doctrine of sanctity of the contract, the terms and conditions set out in the arbitration clause contained in a contract, which parties duly execute, are to be interpreted to give effect of what parties agreed.⁴⁸

Another principle underlying the arbitration agreement is that this clause is independent and separate from the contract in which it is contained.⁴⁹ The principle of

⁴¹ Under Section 10 of the Kenya Arbitration Act, two possibilities are permitted where the court can intervene in arbitration. Firstly, where the Act expressly provides for or permits the intervention of the court; and, secondly, in public interest, where substantial injustice is likely to be occasioned even though a matter is not provided for in the Act. See especially *Euromec v. Shandong Taikai*, op. cit.

⁴² For instance, Section 10 of the Kenya Arbitration Act provides that, except as provided in the Act, no court would intervene in matters governed by the Act. See particularly *Euromec v. Shandong Taikai*, op. cit; where it was held that Section 10 of the Kenya Arbitration Act enunciates the necessity to curb the court's role in arbitration so as to give effect to that policy. The principle of party autonomy is recognized as a critical precept for guaranteeing that parties are satisfied with results of arbitration. It also helps to achieve the key object of arbitration, that is, to deliver fair resolution of disputes between parties without unnecessary delay and expense. The Act is enacted with the key purpose of increasing party autonomy and minimizing court intervention. See also *Construction Engineers and Builders Ltd. v. Sugar Development Corporation* [1983] TLR 13 (CAT) ('*CE&B v. SDC*'); and *Luganuzo v. Orthodox Church*, op. cit.

⁴³ *Luganuzo v. Orthodox Church*, op. cit.

⁴⁴ *Bahadurali E. Shamji & Another v. The Treasury Registrar & Others* [2002] 1 EA 273 ('*Shamji v. TR*').

⁴⁵ See particularly *Telkom Kenya Ltd. & Another v. Kamconsult Ltd. Nairobi* (Milimani) HCCC NOS. 262 & 267 of 2001 [2001] KLR 683; [2001] 2 EA 574 ('*Telkom v. Kamconsult*'); and *Elite Earthmovers Ltd. v. Machakos County Government & Another* [2020] eKLR ('*Elite Earthmovers v. Machakos County Government*').

⁴⁶ See also *Cable and Wireless v. IBN United Kingdom Ltd* [2002] EWHC 2059 ('*Cable and Wireless v. IBN*'); and *Euromec v. Shandong Taikai*, op. cit.

⁴⁷ *Travelport International Ltd. v. Precise Systems Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Commercial Application No. 359/2011 (Unreported) ('*Travelport v. Precise Systems*').

⁴⁸ *Luganuzo v. Orthodox Church*, op. cit.

⁴⁹ The principles of independence and separability of an arbitration agreement are enshrined in Section 12 of the Tanzania Arbitration Act and Section 7 of the English Arbitration Act, 1996. See also *Plinth Technical Works Ltd. v. Fort Portal Municipal Local Government Council* (CAD/ARB/ 62 of 2017) [2018] UGCADER 3 (16 March 2018) ('*Plinth v. Fort Portal*'). In *Fiona Trust*, op. cit, para. 17, it was held that:

"The principle of separability enacted in section 7 [of the English Arbitration Act, which is in *pari materia* with Section 12 of the Tanzania Arbitration Act] means that the invalidity or rescission of the main contract does not necessarily entail the invalidity or rescission of the arbitration agreement. The arbitration agreement must be treated as a "distinct agreement" and can be void or voidable only on grounds which relate directly to the arbitration agreement. Of course, there may be cases in which the ground upon which the main agreement is invalid is identical with the ground upon which the

independence and separability of the arbitration agreement⁵⁰ was enunciated in *Travelport v. Precise Systems*,⁵¹ where it was held that an arbitration agreement in a contract must be taken to be an independent agreement in that where there is an arbitration agreement and the parties have submitted themselves willingly to arbitration as a dispute resolution mechanism, then such arbitration clause cannot cease to operate on the mere fact that what is being dealt with is different from what is in the main contract or the said contract has been terminated.

However, this general rule has an exception in that; where the main contract under which an arbitration agreement is founded is held to be *void ab initio* the arbitration agreement is also held to be void and unenforceable. In principle, this exception is derived from Article V.I of the Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards, 1958 ('New York Convention') and Section 83(2)(a)(i) (aa), (bb), (ii) and (4)(a) of the Tanzania Arbitration Act (2020). These provisions stipulate essentially that an arbitration agreement may be voided on grounds that: (i) parties to the arbitration agreement lacked capacity to enter into the agreement; (ii) parties to the arbitration agreement were not properly represented; and (iii) the arbitration agreement is not valid under the law to which the parties have subjected it.

The leading authority for invalidating an arbitration agreement based on illegality and parties' incapacity was determined by the court in *COPBT v. Monaban*⁵² where an arbitration agreement was held *void ab initio* because the purported contract under which it was purported to have been made was also held to be *void ab initio*. In particular, the court held that: 'the basis of jurisdiction to arbitrate is the parties' valid agreement. If one is to put it differently, as a matter of law, it is the parties' arbitration agreement which constitutes the foundation of the arbitrator's jurisdiction and not otherwise.' In this case, the court found that there was no valid agreement between the parties for want of capacity to create it and, for that matter, no arbitration agreement ever existed between the parties vesting the arbitrator with jurisdiction to determine the matter.

arbitration agreement is invalid. For example, if the main agreement and the arbitration agreement are contained in the same document and one of the parties claims that he never agreed to anything in the document and that his signature was forged, that will be an attack on the validity of the arbitration agreement. But the ground of attack is not that the main agreement was invalid. It is that the signature to the arbitration agreement, as a "distinct agreement", was forged. Similarly, if a party alleges that someone who purported to sign as agent on his behalf had no authority whatever to conclude any agreement on his behalf, that is an attack on both the main agreement and the arbitration agreement.'

⁵⁰ According to Section 12 of the Tanzania Arbitration Act (2020), 'Unless otherwise agreed by the parties, an arbitration agreement which forms or was intended to form part of another agreement, whether or not in writing, shall not be regarded as invalid, non-existent or ineffective because that other agreement is invalid, did not come into existence or has become ineffective, and the arbitration agreement shall for that purpose, be treated as a distinct agreement.'

⁵¹ *Travelport v. Precise Systems*, op. cit.

⁵² *Cereals and Other Produce Board of Tanzania v. Monaban Trading & Farming Co. Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Cause No. 9 of 2022 (Unreported) ('*COPBT v. Monaban*').

2.2 Essential ingredients in an arbitration agreement

It should be noted from the onset that an agreement to arbitrate can take the form of a stand-alone ‘arbitration agreement’ or, more frequently, as a provision within a dispute resolution clause.⁵³ Although there is no specific form of an arbitration agreement,⁵⁴ there are several fundamental ingredients that must be contained in it. It should be noted from the onset that; when drafting an arbitration agreement, care needs to be taken to ensure that such a clause is ‘appropriate for the particular circumstances of the case’⁵⁵ and to avoid rendering it being ambiguous and unenforceable.

Universally, an arbitration agreement must be in writing.⁵⁶ An arbitration agreement must be founded in the underlying principle of law of contract that requires the parties thereto to have capacity to contract – *i.e.*, the parties must be legally competent to enter into contract in which an arbitration is contained.⁵⁷ Because it is taken as a binding contract,⁵⁸ the parties to an arbitration agreement must possess capacity to contract, lack of which vitiates both the founding contract and the arbitration agreement. For instance, in *COPBT v. Monaban*, where there was no valid agreement between the parties for want of capacity to create it, it was held that no arbitration agreement ever existed between the parties vesting the arbitrator with jurisdiction to determine the matter. In that case, the court held that:

Much as the doctrine of severability applies to an arbitral agreement, if the underlying agreement is itself a nullity for want of capacity to create it, in the circumstance of the case at hand, the same effect will definitely permeate to the arbitral agreement because, the same argument would be marshalled in that, it was agreed by parties with no capacity to contract.⁵⁹

In addition, the arbitration agreement should be valid, as a separate contract from the main contract in which it is contained,⁶⁰ in the sense that the object of the contract must

⁵³ Burges Salmon, “Arbitration Basics: Key Ingredients for the Arbitration Agreement,” 16 August 2022; available at <https://www.burges-salmon.com/news-and-insight/legal-updates/disputes/burges-salmon-arbitration-basics-key-ingredients-for-the-arbitration-agreement> (accessed 11 February 2025).

⁵⁴ Mishra, V., “Essential Elements of an Arbitration Agreement,” Lex-Warrier, 1 July 2013; available at <http://www.journal.lex-warrier.in/2013/07/01/essential-elements-of-an-arbitration-agreement/> (accessed 11 February 2023).

⁵⁵ See Sutton, D.S.J., *et al.*, *Russell on Arbitration* (24th edn.) (London: Sweet & Maxwell, 2015), p. 61.

⁵⁶ See, for example, Section 7(3) of the Indian Arbitration and Conciliation Act (1996), Section 10(1) and (3) of the Tanzania Arbitration Act (2020), Section 5(1) and (2) of the English Arbitration Act (Cap. 23 of 1996), Section 4(2) of the Kenya Arbitration Act (Cap. 49), and Section 3(2) of the Uganda Arbitration and Conciliation Act (Cap. 4).

⁵⁷ Kumar, *op. cit.*

⁵⁸ *Luganuzza v. Orthodox Church*, *op. cit.*

⁵⁹ *COPBT v. Monaban*, *op. cit.*, p. 23.

⁶⁰ See particularly Section 7 of the English Arbitration Act; and Section 12 of the Tanzania Arbitration Act. In *Travelport International Ltd. v. Precise Systems Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Commercial Application No. 359/2011 (Unreported) (*Travelport v. Precise Systems*), it was held that an arbitration agreement in a contract must be taken to be an independent and separate agreement such that it survives the main contract even where it is vitiated by various reasons. Similarly, in *Fiona v. Privalov*, *op. cit.*, it was held that:

be lawful and capable of being carried into effect.⁶¹ To achieve this, conspicuously, the arbitration agreement should be crafted in such a manner that it will make it certainly clear and capable of being enforced.

Moreover, the arbitration agreement should expressly stipulate that any present or future disputes in connection with or in relation to the contract in which it is contained will be referred to arbitration.⁶² It should be noted that, such dispute ‘must arise out of the defined legal relationship’; and, as such, a dispute not arising from the legal relationship is beyond the scope of the arbitration agreement.⁶³ In such arbitration agreement, the parties must consensually agree in writing to be bound by the decision of the arbitrator(s).⁶⁴

Another essential ingredient of an arbitration agreement is that the parties must have the intention to refer any disputes arising out of or under the contract in which the arbitration agreement is contained to arbitration.⁶⁵ It should be noted that, as it is the case with the consent inherent in a contract, the consent of the parties to an arbitration agreement must not be influenced by fraud.⁶⁶ The intention of the parties to refer disputes to arbitration is framed in the underlying principle of law of contract to the effect that a binding contract requires parties to be at consensus *ad idem*.⁶⁷ Viewed in this sense, an arbitration agreement should indicate the parties’ consensual agreement on a number of basic elements: the appointment of arbitrators (including the number and manner of their appointment),⁶⁸ the juridical seat of arbitration and the location of any hearing or meeting,⁶⁹ choice of forum⁷⁰ and language of arbitration,⁷¹ choice and determination of

‘17. The principle of separability enacted in section 7 means that the invalidity or rescission of the main contract does not necessarily entail the invalidity or rescission of the arbitration agreement. The arbitration agreement must be treated as a “distinct agreement” and can be void or voidable only on grounds which relate directly to the arbitration agreement. Of course, there may be cases in which the ground upon which the main agreement is invalid is identical with the ground upon which the arbitration agreement is invalid. For example, if the main agreement and the arbitration agreement are contained in the same document and one of the parties claims that he never agreed to anything in the document and that his signature was forged, that will be an attack on the validity of the arbitration agreement. But the ground of attack is not that the main agreement was invalid. It is that the signature to the arbitration agreement, as a “distinct agreement”, was forged. Similarly, if a party alleges that someone who purported to sign as agent on his behalf had no authority whatever to conclude any agreement on his behalf, that is an attack on both the main agreement and the arbitration agreement.’

⁶¹ Kumar, op. cit.

⁶² *Bihar State Mineral Development Corporation v. Encon Builders (I) (P) Ltd.* [2003] 7 SCC 418 (*Bihar v. Encon*’).

⁶³ Kumar, op. cit.

⁶⁴ *Bihar v. Encon*, op. cit.

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶⁶ Kumar, op. cit.

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

⁶⁸ See particularly Sections 15-16 of the English Arbitration Act, Sections 11-17 of the Kenya Arbitration Act, Sections 19-33 of the Tanzania Arbitration Act (2020), and Section 11 of the Uganda Arbitration and Conciliation Act.

⁶⁹ Section 21 of the Kenya Arbitration Act,

⁷⁰ *Luganuzza v. Orthodox Church*, op. cit.

⁷¹ See particularly Section 23 of the Kenya Arbitration Act; and Section 22 of the Uganda Arbitration and Conciliation Act.

the law governing the contract and the rules of procedure governing the arbitration (*lex arbitri*),⁷² and other procedural aspects.⁷³

In addition, the arbitration agreement should set out the jurisdiction and powers of the arbitral tribunal.⁷⁴ In arbitral proceedings, the arbitrator derives his/her jurisdiction from the arbitration clause, and she or he cannot act outside it as doing so will render the decision a nullity.⁷⁵ This power also entails the parties' freedom and autonomy to agree in what circumstances the authority of an arbitrator may be revoked⁷⁶ as well as the termination of the mandate and substitution of arbitrator.⁷⁷

In addition to the foregoing essential ingredients of an arbitration agreement, the Indian Supreme Court has outlined several attributes of an arbitration agreement. In *Modi v. Modi*,⁷⁸ the court listed the following elements as attributes of a contemporary arbitration agreement: (i) the arbitration agreement must contemplate that the decision of the arbitrator(s) will be binding on the parties to the agreement; (ii) the arbitration agreement must indicate that the jurisdiction of the arbitrator(s) to determine the rights of the parties must derive from either the parties' consent, the order of the court, or a statute;⁷⁹ (iii) the arbitration agreement must contemplate that the substantive rights of the parties will be determined by the arbitrator(s); (iv) the arbitration agreement must indicate that the arbitrator(s) will determine the rights of the parties in an impartial and judicial manner with the arbitral tribunal owing an equal obligation of fairness towards both sides;⁸⁰ and (v) the arbitration agreement must contemplate that the arbitral tribunal will make a decision upon a dispute which is already formulated at the time when a reference to the tribunal is made.

To sum up, an effective arbitration agreement is supposed to contain the following fundamental elements: (i) the existence of a valid commercial or investment contract; (ii) the arbitration agreement must be valid and binding in nature (*i.e.*, it must have all the essentials of a valid contract, including the arbitrability of its the subject matter, proper identification of the parties, and a clear reference of the dispute to arbitration – is it some or all disputes that are arbitrable?);⁸¹ (iii) the governing law of the contract and the arbitration agreement; (iv) the *lex arbitri*; (v) the number of arbitrators and the procedure as well as the manner of their appointment (is there any appointing authority? Any qualification for members of the tribunal?); (vi) the juridical seat and venue of arbitration; (vii) the language and costs of arbitration; (viii) whether an *ad hoc* or

⁷² See particularly Section 19 of the Uganda Arbitration and Conciliation Act, and Section 20 of the Kenya Arbitration Act.

⁷³ *Sushila Seth v. State of MP*, AIR 1980 Del 244.

⁷⁴ See particularly Section 38(1) of the English Arbitration Act; *Luganuzo v. Orthodox Church*, op. cit; and *Medical Store Department v. Cool Care Services*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Consolidated Misc. Commercial Causes Nos. 13 & 32/2020 (Unreported) ('*MSD v. Cool Care*').

⁷⁵ *MSD v. Cool Care*, ibid. See also *Mvita Construction Co. Ltd. v. Tanzania Harbour Authority*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania, Civil Appeal No. 94/2001 (Unreported) ('*Mvita v. THA*'); and *Marine Services v. Gas Entec*, op. cit.

⁷⁶ Section 23 of the English Arbitration Act, and Section 27 of the Tanzania Arbitration Act.

⁷⁷ Section 16 of the Kenya Arbitration Act and Section 15 of the Uganda Arbitration and Conciliation Act.

⁷⁸ *KK. Modi v. K.N. Modi*, AIR, 1998, SCC 1297 ('*Modi v. Modi*').

⁷⁹ See, for instance, Section 33 of the Tanzania Investment Act (No. 10 of 2022).

⁸⁰ Treading on this principle, Section 37(1)(a) of the Tanzania Arbitration Act obliges the arbitral tribunal to 'act fairly and impartially as between the parties, giving each party a reasonable opportunity of putting his case and dealing with that of his opponent.'

⁸¹ Sutton, *et al.*, op. cit.

institutional arbitration; (ix) mutuality; (x) confidentiality of arbitral proceedings; and (xi) acceptance of arbitral award as final, binding and enforceable.

According to Judge Gonzi, for there to exist a valid arbitration agreement, the following minimum requirements should be met: (i) the arbitration agreement ‘must arise out of mutual consent’ – *i.e.*, the parties’ consent is ‘the basic requirement for the arbitration agreement’;⁸² (ii) the parties’ intention to submit to arbitration ‘must unequivocally arise from the arbitration agreement’;⁸³ (iii) there must be ‘an obligation on the parties to submit their dispute to arbitration’;⁸⁴ (iv) the agreement ‘must specifically provide for “arbitration”, rather than another process of dispute resolution’;⁸⁵ and (v) the agreement ‘must have originated from the parties’ free will.’⁸⁶ Therefore, the fact that parties to an arbitration agreement have mutually agreed that the ensuing arbitral award is final, binding and enforceable requires that; once the award is rendered, the parties should immediately satisfy it. Failure to honour the arbitral award entitles the award-creditor to access the court to have it enforced.

3. AN OVERVIEW OF THE RECOGNITION AND ENFORCEMENT OF ARBITRAL AWARDS IN TANZANIA

The general rule of arbitration law and practice is that, after an arbitral award is delivered, the award-debtor (*i.e.*, the losing party) is required to satisfy it⁸⁷ in that it consensually consented to resort to arbitration whose outcome is final, binding and enforceable.⁸⁸ However, where the award-debtor does not satisfy it, the arbitral award should be filed in court for recognition and enforcement as a decree of the court.⁸⁹ Where the award-debtor fails to honour an arbitral award, it is the duty of the award-creditor (*i.e.*, the party in whose favour the award was decided) to cause the arbitrator to have the award filed in court of competent jurisdiction, if that party wants to have it enforced as a decree of the court.⁹⁰

⁸² *Tanganyika Wattle v. Dolphin Bay Chemicals*, *op. cit.*, p. 23.

⁸³ *Ibid.*

⁸⁴ *Ibid.* (elaborating that: ‘This sense of obligation to submit themselves to arbitration is underscored by the use of the words “agreement by the parties to submit to arbitration” or the phrase that the parties “undertake to submit to arbitration”, their disputes. These expressions mean that the arbitration agreement must contain a mandatory, rather than permissive, undertaking by the parties to refer their dispute to arbitration.’).

⁸⁵ *Ibid.* (holding that: ‘All the four sources I have displayed above, contain this requirement of clear reference to arbitration as the chosen ADR process. That is, the parties to the agreement must explicitly have mentioned and agreed on arbitration as the process of dispute resolution.’).

⁸⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 24 (concluding that: ‘if one of them has acted while induced by error or as a consequence of fraud, coercion or undue influence, there has been no real consent and the agreement to arbitrate is not valid. This requirement for parties’ free will arises naturally given that it is an arbitration “agreement”. There can be no valid and enforceable agreement in the absence of the parties’ free will.’).

⁸⁷ See particularly *Patel v. Patel*, *op. cit.*; and *Claus Bremer Associates Ltd. v. The Office of Chief Court Administrator, Judiciary of Tanzania*, Misc. Commercial Application No. 50/2020: High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Court) (Unreported) (‘*Claus Bremer v. Chief Court Administrator*’).

⁸⁸ See particularly Sections 65, 73, 83 and 84 of the Arbitration Act (Cap. 15 R.E. 2020).

⁸⁹ *Claus Bremer v. Chief Court Administrator*, *op. cit.* See also *The Higher Education Students’ Loans Board v. Tanzania Building Works Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Cause. 39 of 2022 (Unreported) (‘*HESLB v. TBW*’) (holding that: ‘Ordinarily, where a party who is required to satisfy the award fails to voluntarily satisfy it, usually the other party will proceed to the court with a view to have it registered/recognised as binding and enforceable as would be a judgment or order of the court.’).

⁹⁰ *Claus Bremer v. Chief Court Administrator*, *ibid.*

Like in ordinary civil proceedings, the enforcement of an arbitral award in arbitral proceedings is very crucial. In principle, the enforcement of an award seeks to ensure that the winning party realizes their entitlements as awarded by the arbitral tribunal. As the court held in *HESLB v. TBW*,⁹¹ the filing, recognition and enforcement of an arbitral award are ‘done in a staged process.’⁹² From a legal point of view, there are, in essence, two main substantive provisions which apply to that process – *i.e.*, Sections 73 and 83 of the Arbitration Act (2020).⁹³

As considered below, there are two sets of the procedure for enforcement of arbitral awards in Tanzania: (i) the procedure for enforcing an arbitral award arising from court-annexed arbitral proceedings; and (ii) the procedure for enforcing domestic and foreign arbitral awards rendered in out-of-court arbitral proceedings.

3.1 The recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards arising from court-annexed arbitral proceedings

Court-ordered arbitral proceedings are conducted in terms of the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules (1968).⁹⁴ Once the arbitrator renders the award in court-annexed arbitral proceedings, he is obliged to remit the matter back to the court that appointed him to preside over such proceedings for enforcement. As a general rule, upon receipt of the arbitral award, the presiding judicial officer is obliged to render it as a decree of the court. However, exceptionally, the court may refuse to do so and, instead thereof, remit the award back to the arbitrator for re-consideration as considered below.

3.1.1 Procedure for the recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards arising from court-ordered arbitral proceedings

In terms of Rule 16(1) of the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules (1968), the court that referred the matter to arbitration is obliged to proceed to pronounce judgment according to the award where: (i) it sees no cause to remit the award or any of the matters referred to arbitration for re-consideration in the manner stated in Rule 14;⁹⁵ (ii) an application has been made to set aside the award or the court has refused such application, and (iii) after the time for making such application has expired. Therefore, after the judgment is pronounced, a decree of the court is entered in terms of the award. In that case, no appeal

⁹¹ *HESLB v. TBW*, *op. cit.*

⁹² *Ibid*, p. 16

⁹³ Section 83(1) provides expressly that: ‘Upon application in writing to the court, a domestic arbitral award [...] shall be recognised as binding and enforceable.’ On its part, Section 73 provides expressly that:

‘73.- (1) An award made by the arbitral tribunal pursuant to an arbitration agreement may, by leave of the court, be enforced in the same manner as a judgment or order of the court.

(2) Where leave of the court is given, judgment may be entered in terms of an award.

(3) Save as otherwise provided, leave to enforce an award shall not be given where, or to the extent that, the person against whom it is sought to be enforced shows that the arbitral tribunal lacked substantive jurisdiction to make the award.’

⁹⁴ The Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules, G.N. No. 376 of 1968.

⁹⁵ Notably, Rule 14 of the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules provides expressly that:

‘14. The court may remit the award or any matter referred to arbitration to the reconsideration of the same arbitrator or umpire, upon such terms as it thinks fit-

(a) where the award has left undetermined any of the matters referred to arbitration; where it determines any matter not referred to arbitration, unless such matter can be separated without affecting the determination of the matters referred;

(b) where the award is so indefinite as to be incapable of execution; or

(c) where an objection to the legality of the award is apparent upon the face of it.’

will lie from such decree; except in so far as the decree is in excess of, or not in accordance with, the award.⁹⁶

It should be noted that; the end result of the filed arbitral awards under the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules (1968) is a ‘judgment in a suit and decree of the court’.⁹⁷ This means that the arbitral award rendered under the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules (1968) ultimately ‘diffuses into and is absorbed by “Judgment on award”’ and that happens ‘regardless of whether the arbitration was initiated by order of the court or by the parties without the intervention of the court.’⁹⁸ As such, subsequent to filing an award made under the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules (1968), there ‘will be no arbitral award in existence anymore for recognition and enforcement in a domestic or foreign jurisdiction’ instead there will be a ‘court's judgment on award.’⁹⁹

3.1.2 Circumstances where an award may be remitted to the arbitrator for reconsideration

Although it is obliged to pronounce judgment in favour of the arbitral award as soon as it is presented to it by the arbitrator, the court may defer doing so and may remit the award or any matter referred to arbitration for reconsideration of the same by the arbitrator or umpire.¹⁰⁰ Under Rule 14 of the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules (1968), the following are the circumstances in which the court may remit the award or any matter referred to arbitration to the arbitrator or umpire for reconsideration – that is, where: (i) the award has left undetermined any of the matters referred to arbitration; (ii) the award determines any matter not referred to arbitration, unless such matter can be separated without affecting the determination of the matters so referred; (iii) the award is so indefinite as to be incapable of execution; or (iv) an objection as to the legality of the award is apparent upon the face of it.

3.2 The recognition and enforcement of domestic and foreign arbitral awards made in out-of-court arbitral proceedings

As noted above, the purpose of an arbitration agreement is that the parties should resolve their disputes through arbitration, which (unless the parties agree otherwise) produces an arbitral award that is final, binding upon the parties¹⁰¹ and capable of being enforced.¹⁰² In *Luganuzza v. Orthodox Church*,¹⁰³ it was held that when parties to a contract choose to subject themselves to the arbitration process, they are subjecting themselves to the process which is legally binding to them and may impact on their rights. As such, parties are obliged to ‘undertake to carry out the award without delay.’¹⁰⁴ In *Patel v. Patel*,¹⁰⁵ it was held that parties are obliged to live and abide by the terms and

⁹⁶ Ibid, Rule 16(2).

⁹⁷ *M/S Lukumbulu Investment Co. Ltd. v. St. Anthony Secondary School*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Commercial Application No. 184 of 2015 (Unreported) (*Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Secondary School*), p. 35.

⁹⁸ Ibid.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰⁰ Rule 14 of the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules.

¹⁰¹ Section 65(1) of the Arbitration Act; and Regulation 50(1) of the Arbitration Regulations.

¹⁰² Sections 73(1) and Section 83(1) of the Arbitration Act:

¹⁰³ *Luganuzza v. Orthodox Church*, op. cit.

¹⁰⁴ Regulation 50(2) of the Arbitration Regulations.

¹⁰⁵ *Patel v. Patel*, op. cit.

conditions set out in the final arbitral award. Typically, a party against whom an arbitral award has been made (*i.e.*, the award-debtor) is obliged to honour it as soon it is made.¹⁰⁶

However, in most cases, unsuccessful parties do not do so; hence, the need arises for the successful party (*i.e.*, the award-creditor) to execute the award in court.¹⁰⁷ In *HESLB v. TBW*,¹⁰⁸ it was held that:

Ordinarily, where a party who is required to satisfy the award fails to voluntarily satisfy it, usually the other party will proceed to the court with a view to have it registered or recognised as binding and enforceable as would be a judgment or order of the court.

Therefore, it is the duty of the award-creditor to request the arbitrator to file or to cause the award to be filed in court for registration as soon as it is published.¹⁰⁹ As the court held in *Claus Bremer v. Chief Court Administrator*,¹¹⁰ once an award is issued (unless the other party pays the amount awarded to the award-creditor immediately thereafter without further hustles), it is the duty of the award-creditor to cause the arbitrator to have the award filed in court of competent jurisdiction, if that party wants to have it enforced as a decree of the court. In particular, Section 83(1) of the Arbitration Act provides expressly that upon application in writing to the court, a domestic arbitral award or foreign arbitral award shall be recognized as binding and enforceable.

Under Section 73(1) of the Arbitration Act, an award made by the arbitral tribunal pursuant to an arbitration agreement ‘may, by leave of the court, be enforced in the same manner as a judgment or order of the court’ (*i.e.*, as a decree of the court¹¹¹). Where leave of the court is given, judgment ‘may be entered in terms of an award.’¹¹² However, leave to enforce an award ‘shall not be given where, or to the extent that, the person against whom it is sought to be enforced shows that the arbitral tribunal lacked substantive jurisdiction to make the award.’¹¹³

It should be noted from the outset that; in Tanzania, foreign arbitral awards can be enforced in the same manner as domestic arbitral awards as set out in Section 83(1) of the Arbitration Act. According to this provision, upon application in writing to the court,

¹⁰⁶ Under Regulation 50(3) of the Arbitration Regulations, the arbitral tribunal may fix a time limit (in the arbitral award) for the losing party ‘to comply with the award and impose penalty and/or interest at commercial rates for failure so to do.’ See also *Tanzania Rural and Urban Road Agency (TARURA) v. Canopies International (T) Ltd.* (Misc. Commercial Application No. 23355 of 2024) [2025] TZHCComD 15 (21 February 2025) (*TARURA v. Canopies*).

¹⁰⁷ Mashamba, J.C., *International Arbitration in East Africa* (Dar es Salaam: LexLaw Publishing and Dispute Resolution & Management Ltd., 2021).

¹⁰⁸ *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit.

¹⁰⁹ *Lazafa Co. Ltd. v. World Vision Tanzania* (Misc. Commercial Application 89 of 2021) [2021] TZHCComD 3383 (01 October 2021) (*Lazafa v. WVT*).

¹¹⁰ *Claus Bremer v. Chief Court Administrator*, op. cit.

¹¹¹ See particularly *Mandani v. Suchale* 1971) HCD no. 10 (holding that that an arbitral award is a decree capable of being enforced in a court of law); *TANESCO v. Dowans*, op. cit; and *M/S Kiundo Enterprises (T) Ltd. v. Ardhi University*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Miscellaneous Commercial Cause No. 272 of 2015 (Unreported) (*Kiundo v. AU*).

¹¹² Section 83(2) of the 2020 Arbitration Act.

¹¹³ *Ibid*, Section 83(3).

a foreign arbitral award is recognised as binding and enforceable. The enforcement of foreign arbitral awards in Tanzania is also governed by the Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (1958) ('the New York Convention').¹¹⁴ However, an award may be refused if it is proven under Article V(1)(e) of the New York Convention that the 'award has not yet become binding on the parties.'¹¹⁵ While the five grounds for refusal in Article V of the NY Convention are permissive, not mandatory;¹¹⁶ and there is a presumption under Article III of the NY Convention that an award is binding and should be enforced.¹¹⁷

It should also be noted that; when an arbitral award is sought to be recognized and enforced, the court should make a three-fold initial determination: (i) is there a valid contract between the parties? (ii) if so, does it contain a valid, enforceable arbitration provision? (iii) are the issues in dispute referable to arbitration?¹¹⁸

4. PROCEDURAL STEPS IN RECOGNIZING AND ENFORCING ARBITRAL AWARDS

The adoption of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations ('the Arbitration Regulations') in January 2021¹¹⁹ has expressly entrenched the procedural steps in enforcing arbitral awards in Tanzania. Before these Regulations were adopted, there were contracting positions in the High Court as to what was exactly the requisite procedural steps for enforcing arbitral awards in court. Before the adoption of the Arbitration Regulations (2021), the Arbitration Rules (1957)¹²⁰ regulated procedure for enforcement of arbitral awards in Tanzania.

Under the repealed arbitration law regime, arbitral awards were only enforced in the High Court where there were two ways of enforcing arbitral awards. The first one was that an award had to be filed in the court for registration as a decree of the court.¹²¹ Accordingly, the arbitral award was not necessarily required to 'be brought before a judge

¹¹⁴ *TANESCO v. Dowans*, op. cit.

¹¹⁵ In *X v. Y*, the Higher Regional Court of Cologne enforced the award, stating that the parties did not agree to a review of the arbitral award at a higher arbitral instance and 'an arbitral award is deemed binding on the parties when it cannot be impugned, either before a higher arbitral instance or by a means of recourse in court.' The court also stated that the status of an appeal at the seat of arbitration does not affect the binding nature of the award: "[T]he possibility to have the award set aside in the state of rendition through a means similar to the German request for annulment [...] does not hinder [the award being] binding. [...] This is also true when such annulment proceeding has already been commenced. [...] [I]n the present case it must therefore be held that the arbitral award is binding, notwithstanding the still pending annulment proceeding before the competent court of appeal of Milan.'

¹¹⁶ In affirming the denial of enforcement, the D.C. Circuit Court held, in *Diag Human S.E. v. Czech Republic - Ministry of Health* (No. 1:13-cv-00355), that: under the parties' arbitration agreement, 'the parties had recourse to another arbitration panel, which was sufficient to prevent the award from becoming binding.'

¹¹⁷ Born, G., *International Commercial Arbitration* (2nd edn.) (Kluwer International Law, 2014), pp. 3428-3430:

¹¹⁸ *Tanganyika Wattle v. Dolphin Bay*, op. cit.

¹¹⁹ The Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (G.N. No. 146 of 2021).

¹²⁰ The 1957 Arbitration Rules were made under Section 20 of the repealed Arbitration Act.

¹²¹ *Kiundo Enterprises (T) Ltd. v. Ardhi University*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Cause No. 272/2015 (Unreported) ('*Kiundo v. AU*').

to make an order to have the arbitral award an enforceable decree.’¹²² The second way was that: ‘once an arbitral award [had] been filed in court, the process of having it transformed into a decree of the court follow[ed]’¹²³ – *i.e.*, the arbitral award was ‘taken before a judge who summon[ed] the parties and [told] them the filing of the award and if a respondent intimate[d] not to take any step to challenge it, the same [was] recorded and, by order, [became] enforceable.’¹²⁴

Indeed, the Court of Appeal supported the second way of enforcement of an arbitral award. For example, in *TCMB v. Cogecot*,¹²⁵ it stated that:

So far in our country the practice in matters of arbitration awards is that the court is moved by an application for an order for filing which is then followed by proceedings. On the basis of the Indian decisions, we are persuaded to take the view that as a matter of law it is unnecessary to conduct proceedings before an order for filing is made, the receipt of the award by the Court Registry constitutes the filing of the award. Thereafter, the court is required to notify the parties who may wish to challenge or to enforce the award in terms of the law.

This means that; before the adoption of the 2021 Arbitration Regulations, a party wishing to enforce an arbitral award could follow any of the two procedural steps to commence enforcement proceedings in the High Court. However, now this contradiction has been rectified by the Arbitration Regulations, as canvassed below.

In fact, the 2021 Arbitration Regulations have codified the second method of filing an award in court for registration, recognition and enforcement as a decree of the court. These Regulations also have widened the scope of the enforcing court – from arbitral awards being only enforced in the High Court to the same being enforced in the court of competent jurisdiction, which may be the High Court, the Resident Magistrate’s Court or the District Court.¹²⁶ Therefore, the procedural steps for filing, registration, recognition and enforcement of an arbitral award in court are elaborated in the next sections of this article.

5. PROCEDURAL STEP 1: FILING THE ARBITRAL AWARD IN A COURT OF COMPETENT JURISDICTION

The first procedural step for enforcing an arbitral award is the filing of the award in a court of competent jurisdiction. As such, before the court is seized with the award, it has

¹²² Ibid. See also *M/S Lukumbulu Investment Co. Ltd. v. M/S St. Anthony Secondary School*, High Court of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Application No.184 of 2015 (Unreported) (*Lukumbulu v. St. Anthony Sec. School*).

¹²³ *Kiundo v. AU*, *ibid.*

¹²⁴ Ibid.

¹²⁵ *Tanzania Cotton Marketing Board v. Cogecot Cotton Company SA* [1997] TLR 165 (*TCMB v. Cogecot*).

¹²⁶ Section 6 of the Arbitration Act (2020).

to be filed in court by way of a letter.¹²⁷ Under both the previous and current arbitration legal regimes, either the arbitrator or any of the parties may cause the award to be filed and subsequently registered in court.¹²⁸ Before we proceed to examine the mode of filing an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement, we elaborate the meaning of the term ‘filing of the award in court’.

(a) What constitutes ‘filing of the award in court’?

The term “filing of an award in court” under the arbitration legislation was recently elaborated in *TARURA v. Canopies*.¹²⁹ In that case, the court was mindful of the ‘apparent misconception that equates the “filing” of the Award in Court to “recognition” or “registration” of the Award for enforcement.’¹³⁰ According to Judge Gonzi,

Countless times, parties and their counsel petition the Court seeking recognition and enforcement of the award and go through the entire judicial process until an Arbitral Award is “recognised” by the Court as enforceable as a decree of the Court. It is only then that they start to pursue new judicial proceedings in the same Court seeking to challenge the same Award that they have successfully pursued its “recognition” by the Court as an enforceable decree of the Court. To them “filing” is the end result of the entire post award enforcement process. I find that to be wrong.¹³¹

The court cited two matters before it involving the same parties – *i.e.*, *Zawiya (T) Traders Ltd. and Coca Cola Kwanza Ltd.* After the court recognised the arbitral award in *Zawiya Traders v. Coca Cola Kwanza – I*,¹³² the petitioner filed another petition (*Zawiya Traders v. Coca Cola Kwanza – II*)¹³³ challenging the award for certain serious

¹²⁷ *M/S Lukumbulu Investment Co. Ltd. v. St. Anthony Secondary School*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Commercial Application No. 184 of 2015 (Unreported) (*‘Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Secondary School’*).

¹²⁸ Regulation 51(4) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021). In *HESLB v. TBW*, *op. cit.*, it was held that; this position does not differ from the previous position under the Repealed Arbitration Act (Cap.15 R.E. 2002) and its Arbitration Rules (1957). Regulation 51(4) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021) is, to a large extent, identical to what Section 11(2) of the repealed Arbitration Act (Cap.15 R.E. 2002) used to provide. *See also TCMB v. Cogecot*, *op. cit.*

¹²⁹ *Tanzania Rural and Urban Road Agency (TARURA) v. Canopies International (T) Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Application No. 23355 of 2024 (Unreported) (*‘TARURA v. Canopies’*).

¹³⁰ *Ibid*, p. 25.

¹³¹ *Ibid*, pp. 25-26.

¹³² *Zawiya (T) Traders Ltd. v. Coca Cola Kwanza Ltd.* (Misc. Commercial Cause No. 69 of 2023) [2024] TZHCComD 58 (29 April 2024) (*‘Zawiya Traders v. Coca Cola Kwanza – I’*).

¹³³ *Zawiya (T) Traders Ltd. v. Coca-Cola Kwanza Ltd.* (Misc. Commercial Cause No. 74 of 2023) [2024] TZHCComD 100 (31 May 2024) (*‘Zawiya Traders v. Coca Cola Kwanza – II’*).

irregularities.¹³⁴ Commenting on this unusual procedural action, in *TARURA v. Canopies*, the court held that:

It is clear that in the above mentioned two cases, the understanding of the Applicant or Petitioner and her Learned Counsel was that the first application for recognition and enforcement of the arbitral award together with its attendant judicial proceedings and the ultimate order granting the application, were all part and parcel of “filing” the Award in Court for the purpose of challenging it.¹³⁵

Similarly, in *Canopies v. TARURA – I*,¹³⁶ the petitioner filed a petition in court praying for recognition of a domestic arbitral award as binding and enforceable and an application for leave to enforce the said award as judgment of the court and be registered as decree of the court. After hearing the parties, the court ordered that:

Since recognition and enforcement of this Award is not resisted by the Respondent and there is no statutory bar to it, I do hereby make an order for its recognition for enforcement as a Decree of this Court. Ruling and Drawn Order to that effect will issue accordingly.

Subsequent to that order, the same parties (represented by the same advocates) went ahead to litigate in Commercial Application No. 017964 of 2024 (*Canopies v. TARURA – II*)¹³⁷ in the same court. In fact, the same petitioner, who had just secured recognition of its award against the same respondent, actively began challenging the same arbitral award¹³⁸ that had been recognized by the very court in earlier proceedings seeking

¹³⁴ In *Zawiya Traders v. Coca Cola Kwanza – II*, the petitioner (*i.e.*, the award-creditor) challenged the already recognized award on the ground that there existed serious regularities on the face of the award, alleging:

- i. The award exempted the losing party (the respondent) from obligation to pay the successful party (the petitioner) arbitration costs.
- ii. The award has shown open favouritism and bias against the petitioner.
- iii. The tribunal failed to appreciate the impact of the amply established TShs. 1.3 billion loss of business and awarded a nominal TShs. 50 million in general damages which is not commensurate with the loss suffered by the petitioner.'

¹³⁵ *TARURA v. Canopies*, *op. cit.*, p. 29.

¹³⁶ *Canopies International (T) Ltd. v. Tanzania Rural and Urban Roads Agency*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Commercial Application No. 023410 of 2024 (Unreported) (*'Canopies v. TARURA – I'*).

¹³⁷ *Canopies International Ltd. v. Tanzania Rural and Urban Roads Agency*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Commercial Application No. 017964 of 2024 (Unreported) (*'Canopies v. TARURA – II'*).

¹³⁸ In *Canopies v. TARURA – II*, the petitioner sought for the following orders:

1. That the whole Award be set aside on the basis of there being serious irregularities.
2. The Award be declared of no effect.
3. The Court makes an order for a fresh arbitration before another Arbitrator.
4. Costs of the Arbitration be granted.

recognition and enforcement. Commenting on this strange procedural irregularity, in *TARURA v. Canopies*, the court held that:

[...] once again, the understanding of the Applicant and her Learned Counsel [in *Canopies v. TARURA – II*] was that the first application for recognition and enforcement of the arbitral award together with its attendant entire proceedings and the ultimate Court order granting the application, were all just part and parcel of “filing” of the Award in Court for the purpose of challenging it in the subsequent proceedings. The feeling in both cases above referred was that a person aggrieved by an Arbitral Award could not initiate proceedings in Court to challenge the Award until and unless the Award had been filed in Court and further that the filing of an Award entailed the whole process of seeking its recognition for enforcement as a decree of the Court. It was their understanding as well that even the time limit for an application to challenge an Award should be counted from the moment the Award Creditor files the Award in Court for recognition. “Filing” was understood as synonymous to “recognition” or “registration” of the Award.¹³⁹

Therefore, in *TARURA v. Canopies*, the court posed the following question to the parties’ counsel: what does the term ‘filing of an award in court’ entail under Tanzanian arbitration law? According to the court, filing of the arbitral award is ‘the presentation of the award in court for its registration in which case the court is thereby seized with the award which becomes deposited in court.’¹⁴⁰ Similarly, in *HESLB v. TBWL*,¹⁴¹ ‘filing of an award’ was defined to mean an action through which an arbitral award is transmitted to the court for registration.¹⁴² Therefore, as the Court of Appeal held in *TCMB v. Cogecot*,¹⁴³ ‘the receipt of the award by the Court Registry constitutes filing of the award.’¹⁴⁴ Therefore,

Filing of the Award in Court is the first stage towards recognition and enforcement of the Award or its being challenged [...] filing is completed by the receipt of the

5. Any other order (s)/relief this honourable Court may deem just and proper to grant in the interest of justice.’

¹³⁹ *TARURA v. Canopies*, op. cit, pp. 32-33.

¹⁴⁰ Ibid, p. 33.

¹⁴¹ *HESLB v. TBWL*, op. cit.

¹⁴² Ibid, p. 28.

¹⁴³ *Tanzania Cotton Marketing Board v. Cogecot Cotton Company S.A* [2002] TZCA 13 (*TCMB v. Cogecot*’).

¹⁴⁴ The Court of appeal held the same view in *M/S St. Anthony Secondary School v. Lukumbulu Investment Co. Ltd* (Civil Revision No. 388/16 of 2022) [2024] TZCA 123 (23 February 2024) (*St. Anthony Secondary School v. Lukumbulu Investment*’).

award by the Registrar of the High Court. Filing of the Arbitral Award is just the presentation of the Award in Court whereby the Court becomes seized with the Award.¹⁴⁵

In principle, an arbitral award is filed in court for the purpose of either ‘recognition and enforcement or [...] challenging it.’¹⁴⁶

(b) Modes of filing an arbitral award in court

In *HESLB v. TBW*,¹⁴⁷ the court held that; where a party seeks an award to be “recognised” by the court and to be “enforced” as a decree of the court, an application to that effect must ‘be brought under Sections 83(1) and 73(1) of the Arbitration Act, read together with the relevant provisions of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021)’ and such relevant provisions of the Regulations ‘will depend on whether the award is a “domestic” or “foreign” award.’¹⁴⁸

There are two modes of filing an award in court for recognition and enforcement: it may be made either orally or formally (through a *letter* or a formal application).¹⁴⁹ In particular, an application for filing an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement may be made *orally* in terms of Regulation 51(7) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021).¹⁵⁰ On its part, an application for filing an award in court for recognition and enforcement may be made through a *formal application* by a *letter*¹⁵¹ or a *petition*.¹⁵² In either mode of filing of an award in court, one must comply with Section 73 of the Arbitration Act.¹⁵³

In *HESLB v. TBW*, the court held that the phrase “save as it may have been provided otherwise” set out on Regulation 63(1) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021) entails that the provision does recognise that there could be other means than by way of an application in the form of a petition, through which a matter may be brought to the attention of the court. As such, a letter stated in Regulations 49 and 51(4)-(5) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021) is ‘such other means by which an award may be filed in court without adopting the manner provided for under Regulation 63(1), *i.e.*, without filing a petition.’¹⁵⁴ Likewise, an application to the court regarding enforcement of the award, ‘may even, as per Regulation 51(7) provides, be made orally.’¹⁵⁵

¹⁴⁵ *TARURA v. Canopies*, op. cit, pp. 37-38.

¹⁴⁶ *Ibid*, p. 38.

¹⁴⁷ *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit.

¹⁴⁸ *Ibid*.

¹⁴⁹ Regulation 51(7) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021), which provides expressly that: ‘A leave to enforce an award under section 68(1) shall be made *orally* or *by way of an application*.’ (Emphasis supplied). See also *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit.

¹⁵⁰ *Ibid*, Regulation 51(7).

¹⁵¹ *Ibid*, Regulation 51(4).

¹⁵² *Ibid*, Regulation 63(1).

¹⁵³ *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit.

¹⁵⁴ *Ibid*.

¹⁵⁵ *Ibid*.

(i) Filing an award in court through a letter

The filing of an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement through a letter is regulated by Regulation 51(4), (5) and (6) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Rules (2021). As it was held in *Voltalia v. Nextgen*¹⁵⁶ and *TARURA v. Canopies*, under the current arbitration legal regime, there are two alternative ways of filing the award in court for registration through a letter:

- (i) The arbitral tribunal, at the request of any party to the award or any person claiming under him, is *obliged to cause* to be filed in court an arbitral award for registration as a court decree;¹⁵⁷ or
- (ii) The arbitral tribunal *may*, in the letter transmitting the award to the parties, *allow any party* to the proceedings to file a certified copy of the award together with the proceedings thereof with the court for the purposes of registration of the same.¹⁵⁸

As the court reasoned in *Voltalia v. Nextgen*, the filing of an award in court for registration is done by writing a *letter* to the Registrar of the High Court or the Resident Magistrate-in-charge of the District Court or the Court of the Resident Magistrate – depending on the pecuniary jurisdiction of the relevant court. Notably, in case of domestic award, the courts of competent pecuniary jurisdiction are the District Court, the Court of the Resident Magistrate and the High Court; whereas, in the case of a foreign arbitral award, the court of competent jurisdiction is solely the High Court.¹⁵⁹ The letter must be accompanied by the certified copies of the award together with the evidence on reference and the minutes of the proceedings.¹⁶⁰ In *TARURA v. Canopies*, it was held that: ‘The purpose of the letter or petition with which the Award is filed will determine the next steps either seeking its recognition also known as registration or seeking its being challenged under the legally prescribed grounds.’¹⁶¹

It should be noted that; where an award is filed in court under Regulation 51(5) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021), the party so filing it must also attach to the transmittal letter, not only a certified copy of the award but also the

¹⁵⁶ *Voltalia Portugal S.A. v. Nextgen Solawazi Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Commercial Cause No. 7/ 2020 (Unreported) (*Voltalia v. Nextgen*).

¹⁵⁷ Regulation 51(4) of the Arbitration Regulations (GN. No. 146/2021). This provision replicates the provision of Section 12(2) of the repealed Arbitration Act.

¹⁵⁸ *Ibid*, Regulation 51(5). Under this provision, the arbitral tribunal ‘may in the letter transmitting the award to the parties, allow any party to the proceeding to file a certified copy of the award together with the proceedings thereof with the court for the purposes of registration of the same.’

¹⁵⁹ Under Section 6(1) of the Arbitration Act (2020), the term “court” –

‘(a) in relation to domestic arbitration, means the district court, resident magistrate’s court, the High Court exercising its original or appellate jurisdiction or the Court of Appeal; or

(b) in relation to international arbitration, means the High Court in the exercise of its ordinary original civil jurisdiction.’

In terms of sub-section (2) of this provision, the manner of recognition and dealing with foreign arbitration in the United Republic shall be as prescribed in the respective laws governing arbitration. For the purpose of subsection (1)(a) of Section 6, jurisdiction of court shall be in accordance with the Magistrate’s Court Act, Cap. 11 R.E. 2022, and any other written laws [Section 6(3)].

¹⁶⁰ Regulation 51(1), (4), (5) and (6) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021). See also *TARURA v. Canopies*, *op. cit.*, p. 38.

¹⁶¹ *TARURA v. Canopies*, *ibid*, pp. 40-41.

proceedings thereof.¹⁶² However, Regulation 51(4) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021) does not state that when causing the award to be filed in court through a letter what documents need to accompany it. Nevertheless,

[Prudence would call for the transmittal letter] to be filed together with [certified copies of] the proceedings from which the award got derived. This is because, proceedings entail the process which the tribunal went through in arriving at the award and for a court required to recognise an award as binding and enforceable it must be a decision lest it be taken for a ride.¹⁶³

Therefore, in terms of Regulation 51(6) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021), filing of an award ‘is done and is completed even before parties are given notice by the Court to come and address the Court in respect thereof like to show cause why the Award should not be registered.’¹⁶⁴ This means that judicial proceedings relating to challenge or recognition of the award, ‘cannot be done in Court unless the Award is firstly filed/received in Court registry.’¹⁶⁵

(ii) Filing an award in court through a petition

Regulation 63(1)(a) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021) provides categorically that: ‘all applications’ to the court made under the provisions of the Arbitration Act or these Regulation must ‘be made by way of petition’, ‘[save] as is otherwise provided.’ In particular, such petition must be titled: “In the matter of the arbitration and in the matter of the Act” and reference should be made in the application to the relevant section of the Act.¹⁶⁶ The petition should also contain a brief statement – in summary form – of the material facts, which ‘shall be divided into paragraphs numbered consecutively and shall state the nature of the relief sought or the questions of law for the determination of the Court as the case may be.’¹⁶⁷

In addition, the following documents should be annexed to the petition: the submission to arbitration (*i.e.*, the arbitration clause), the minutes or proceedings of the arbitral tribunal,¹⁶⁸ the award or the ruling to which the petition relates, or a copy of it

¹⁶² *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit. In this case, the court was grappled with the question: what constitutes “proceedings” of the arbitral tribunal as envisaged under Regulation 51(5) of Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021)? The court borrowed a definition described in *Black’s Law Dictionary* (10th edn.), at page 1398, thus:

‘The regular and orderly progression of a lawsuit, including all acts and events between the time of commencement and entry of judgement [...]. ‘Proceeding’ is a word much used to express the business done in courts...but it may include in its general sense all steps taken or measures adopted in prosecution or defence of an action, including the pleadings judgement.’

According to the court, this definition ‘fits as well to matters filed before arbitral tribunals or any other tribunals and not only courts of law.’

¹⁶³ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁴ *TARURA v. Canopies*, op. cit p. 41.

¹⁶⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁶ Regulation 63(1)(a) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021).

¹⁶⁷ *Ibid.*, Regulation 63(1)(b).

¹⁶⁸ In *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit.

certified by the petitioner or his/her advocate to be a true copy.¹⁶⁹ Moreover, the petition should specify the persons affected by it and upon whom notice is required to be given as provided in the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021) and should state the address, in detail, of each of them.¹⁷⁰

(c) The legal effect of filing an award in court

In effect, the filing of the award makes the court register and recognise it. Thereafter, the court will proceed to either refuse the award under Section 83(2)(a) and (b) of the Arbitration Act (if there are raised before the court such matters by a party to whom notice to show cause was issued), or have the award enforced subject to the requirements under the provisions of Section 73 of the Arbitration Act.¹⁷¹

6. PROCEDURAL STEP 2: REGISTRATION OF THE ARBITRAL AWARD

The second procedural step for enforcing an arbitral award in court is the registration of the award for the purpose of it being rendered as a decree of the court.¹⁷² Notably, recognition of an award constitutes one of the last procedural stages of the arbitral proceedings.¹⁷³

(a) What constitutes registration of the arbitral award?

In *TARURA v. Canopies*, the court held that ‘registration’ of an award is the process where the court receives the registered award for its “recognition” by the court that ‘the same is enforceable as a decree of the Court.’¹⁷⁴ In the context of arbitration, the registration of an arbitral award generally refers to an action where the officially filed award is registered in the relevant court registry and given a case file number. It effectively paves the way for the assignment of the matter to a presiding magistrate or judge and the issuance of a notice to the parties to appear in court for the subsequent recognition and enforcement of the filed arbitral award, as considered below.

(b) When is registration of the arbitral award deemed to be done?

The registration of an award is done by either the Registrar of the High Court or the Resident Magistrate-in-charge of a District Court or Court of the Resident Magistrate of the court where the award is filed. The registration of the award is *only* made upon payment of the fees and charges due in respect of the arbitration and award and of the costs and charges of filing the award in court.¹⁷⁵ Thereafter, notice of the filing and registration of award must be given to the parties by the concerned arbitrator¹⁷⁶ or the party that has been allowed by the arbitrator to cause the award to be filed in court for registration.¹⁷⁷ It should be note that; the fact that the arbitral award has been registered

¹⁶⁹ Regulation 63(1)(c) and (d) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021).

¹⁷⁰ Ibid, Regulation 63(1)(e).

¹⁷¹ *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit.

¹⁷² *St. Anthony Secondary School v. Lukumbulu Investment*, op. cit.

¹⁷³ *TARURA v. Canopies*, op. cit, p. 42.

¹⁷⁴ Ibid, p. 35.

¹⁷⁵ Regulation 51(4) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021).

¹⁷⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷⁷ Ibid, Regulation 51(4).

in court, ‘does not mean that it has already been recognized as binding and enforceable. The other side can [still] challenge it.’¹⁷⁸

7. PROCEDURAL STEP 3: ISSUANCE OF NOTICE TO THE PARTIES

Once the award is filed and duly registered in court, the court is obliged to issue a notice to the parties and the arbitral tribunal or the arbitral institution that administered the arbitral proceedings in question on the filing and registration of the award in court.¹⁷⁹ Where the award is filed through a letter, the notice should require the parties to the notice ‘to show cause as to why the award should not be registered and enforced pursuant to the provisions of section 73 of the [Arbitration] Act.’¹⁸⁰

Where the award is filed through a petition – within the period of not less than seven days before the date for the hearing of a petition or such lesser time as the presiding Magistrate or the Judge (as the case may be) may allow – written notice thereof ‘shall be given by the court to all persons specified in the petition and to such other persons as appear to likely be affected by the proceedings.’¹⁸¹ Such notice should require such persons ‘to show cause, within the time specified in the notice, why the relief sought should not be granted and, if no sufficient cause be shown, a judge [or magistrate] may make such order as the circumstances of the case may appear to him to require.’

This means that the notice will have the effect of summoning the parties to appear before an assigned Judge or Magistrate for a scheduled hearing as to whether or not the award should be recognised and subsequently enforced. As the Court of Appeal held in *St. Anthony Secondary School v. Lukumbulu Investment*, the court is required to notify the parties who ‘may wish to challenge or to enforce the award in terms of the law.’

8 PROCEDURAL STEP 4: RECOGNITION AND ENFORCEMENT OF THE ARBITRAL AWARD

Both the recognition and enforcement of the arbitral award form a very crucial procedural step towards the execution of an arbitral award as a decree of the court. Recognition and enforcement of an award do run together because ‘one is a necessary part of the other.’¹⁸²

(a) What Constitutes Recognition and Enforcement of the Arbitral Award?

In *HESLB v. TBW*,¹⁸³ the court defined a ‘recognition of an arbitral award’ as ‘a process where a party seeks for an authoritative endorsement of the court, that, the award is “authentic” and, hence, confirmed to be final and binding.’ According to the court, recognition of arbitral awards is, therefore, the first pre-requisite of the three final post-arbitration stages in case an award is not voluntarily executed. The other two subsequent stages after recognition are enforcement of the award and execution of the decree emanating from that enforcement process.¹⁸⁴

¹⁷⁸ *Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Secondary School*, op. cit, p. 21.

¹⁷⁹ Regulations 51(6) and 63(2) of the Arbitration (Rules of Procedure) Regulations (2021).

¹⁸⁰ Regulation 51(6) of the Arbitration Regulations.

¹⁸¹ Ibid, Regulation 63(2).

¹⁸² *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit.

¹⁸³ Ibid.

¹⁸⁴ Referring to Blackaby, N., et al., *Redfern and Hunter on International Arbitration* (6th edn.) (Oxford University Press, 2015), p. 611 (stating that: ‘recognition of award’ entails a process where a party to an

An award is first “recognised” before it is “enforced.” Both in principle and practice, an award is to be “recognised” by the court where it is filed as ‘having the status of being “final” and “binding” on the parties.’¹⁸⁵ This is essentially the case because; in effect, an award ‘may be “provisional” and, hence, not binding on the parties yet. That kind of an inconclusive award may not be enforced.’¹⁸⁶

On its part, ‘enforcement of an arbitral award’ entails a process during which the court ensures that the award “which it had recognised” ‘is carried out by using legal sanctions as are available.’¹⁸⁷ Enforcement of awards, therefore, involves the ‘act of converting the award into concrete relief for the claimant upon which he can rely upon to commence execution proceedings.’¹⁸⁸ As such, this process is regarded as a step further than “recognition of the award”.¹⁸⁹

But what is the difference between recognition and enforcement of an arbitral award? In *TARURA v. Canopies*, the court quoted at length a passage in an article by Tecele Hagos Bahta, who points out that:

Briefly put, the difference between recognition and enforcement is that, an award may be recognized, without being enforced; but if it is enforced, then it is necessarily recognized by the Court which orders its enforcement. Thus, an award-creditor may seek only for its recognition or its recognition and enforcement.¹⁹⁰

What are the purposes of recognition and enforcement of an arbitral award? Tecele Hagos Bahta elaborates the purposes of recognition and enforcement of an arbitral award as follows:

The purpose of recognition on its own is to act as a shield; it is used to block any attempt to initiate fresh proceedings, issues which have already been decided in the arbitration that gave rise to the award whose recognition is sought. The purpose of enforcement is, however, to act as a sword, not a shield. The recognition of an award by a Court gives a *res judicata* effect thereto. Enforcement, however, goes a step

award asks the court to ‘recognize an award as valid and binding upon the parties in respect of the issues with which it dealt.’).

¹⁸⁵ *HESLB v. TBW*, op. cit.

¹⁸⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁸⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁸⁹ *Ibid.*, quoting Blackaby, N., *et al.*, *Redfern and Hunter on International Arbitration*, op. cit, thus:

‘A court that is prepared to grant enforcement of an award will do so because it recognises the award as validly made and binding upon the parties to it, and therefore suitable for enforcement. In this context, the terms ‘recognition’ and ‘enforcement’ do run together: one is a necessary part of the other.’

¹⁹⁰ Bahta, T.H. “Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards in Civil and Commercial Matters in Ethiopia,” *Mizan Law Review*, Vol. 5 No.1, Spring 2011, at p. 108.

further than recognition. As Redfern and Hunter noted, where a Court is asked to enforce an award, it is asked not merely to recognize the legal force and effect of the award, but also to ensure that it is carried out by using such legal sanctions as are available. Thus, the terms ‘recognition’ and ‘enforcement’ can be used together where the latter is the necessary follow-up of the former in judgments and awards which carry pecuniary obligations. The difference between ‘recognition’ and ‘enforcement’ is further summarized as follows: Recognition is an undertaking by a state to respect the bindingness of foreign arbitral awards. Such awards may be relied upon by way of defence or set-off in any legal proceedings concerning the subject-matter of the award commenced in the Courts of the state concerned, whereas enforcement is an undertaking by a state to enforce foreign arbitral awards, in accordance with its local procedural rules.¹⁹¹

In *TARURA v. Canopies*, the court held that recognition of an arbitral award ‘is used to block any attempt to initiate fresh proceedings, in respect of issues which have already been decided in the arbitration that gave rise to the award whose recognition is sought and granted. Recognition of an award by a Court gives it a *res judicata* effect, among others.’¹⁹²

(b) The procedure for recognition and enforcement of the arbitral award

When the parties or their advocates or other legal representatives enter appearance before the assigned Judge or Magistrate on the scheduled date, the presiding judicial officer should order the parties to address the court as to why the award should be or should not be enforced as a decree of the court. Where a party indicates that it wishes to challenge the award on any of the grounds listed in Section 74 or Section 75 of the Arbitration Act, the presiding judicial officer will order that party to file the relevant petition in terms of Regulation 63 of the Arbitration Regulations (2021). However, where the parties do not wish to challenge the award, the court will recognise and record it as a decree of the court capable of being enforced in accordance with the law.

(c) The legal effect of the recognized award

As it was held in *TARURA v. Canopies*, ‘a recognized award acquires the status of a Decree of the Court’¹⁹³ pursuant to Section 83(1) of the 2020 Arbitration Act;¹⁹⁴ and, therefore, capable of being executed in terms of Sections 31-54 and Order XXI of the Civil Procedure

¹⁹¹ Ibid.

¹⁹² *TARURA v. Canopies*, op. cit, p. 37.

¹⁹³ *TARURA v. Canopies*, op. cit, p. 45.

¹⁹⁴ Section 83(1) of the 2020 Arbitration Act. In principle, Section 84 of the Arbitration Act provides expressly that:

‘84. Where the court is satisfied that the award is enforceable under this Part, the award shall be deemed to be a decree of that court.’

Code ('the CPC'). Therefore, once an arbitral award has been recognized as an enforceable decree of the court, the same award 'cannot subsequently be challenged in the same Court for it to be set aside or remitted for reconsideration.' Similarly, a recognized arbitral award 'cannot be subsequently annulled by the same court.'¹⁹⁵ However, it can only be challenged 'by way of review, appeal or revision against the decree of the Court'¹⁹⁶ in terms of Sections 77, 78 and 85 of the Arbitration Act.

9. COURT'S DISCRETION TO REFUSE REGISTERING AND ENFORCING AN ARBITRAL AWARD

As a general rule, once an award made in out-of-court arbitral proceedings is filed and registered in court, the court is obliged to recognize and render the award as a decree of the court.¹⁹⁷ However, in exceptional circumstances, the court may refuse to recognise and enforce an award. Such exceptional circumstances include:

- (i) Where the party requesting the court to refuse the enforcement of the award has furnished proof to the court that: (a) the parties lacked the capacity to enter into agreement,¹⁹⁸ or (b) the parties were not properly represented in the arbitral proceedings;¹⁹⁹
- (ii) Where the arbitration agreement was not valid under the law to which the parties have subjected it or, failing any indication of that law, under the law of the State where the arbitral award was made;²⁰⁰
- (iii) Where the arbitral award deals with a dispute not contemplated by or not falling within the terms of the reference to arbitration, or it contains decisions on matters beyond the scope of the reference to arbitration; provided that, if the decisions on matters referred to arbitration can be separated from those not so referred, that part of the arbitral award which contains decisions on matters referred to arbitration may be recognised and enforced;²⁰¹
- (iv) Where the parties were not given proper notice on the appointment of arbitrator(s);²⁰²
- (v) Where the composition of the arbitral tribunal was contrary to the parties' agreement;²⁰³
- (vi) Where the arbitral award has not yet become binding on the parties or has been set aside or suspended by a court of the State in which, or under the law of which, that arbitral award was made;²⁰⁴
- (vii) Where the making of the arbitral award was induced or affected by fraud, bribery, corruption or undue influence;²⁰⁵ or

¹⁹⁵ *TARURA v. Canopies*, op. cit, p. 46.

¹⁹⁶ *Ibid*.

¹⁹⁷ *Bogeta Engineering Ltd. v. Nanyumbu District Council*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Comm. Cause No. 9 of 2019 (unreported) ('*Bogeta v. Nanyumbu DC*').

¹⁹⁸ Section 83(2)(a)(i)(aa) of the 2020 Arbitration Act.

¹⁹⁹ *Ibid*, Section 83(2)(a)(i)(bb).

²⁰⁰ *Ibid*, Section 83(2)(a)(ii) and (4)(a).

²⁰¹ *Ibid*, Section 83(2)(a)(iv) and (4)(c).

²⁰² *Ibid*, Section 83(2)(a)(iii) and (4)(b).

²⁰³ *Ibid*, Section 83(2)(a)(v) and (4)(d).

²⁰⁴ *Ibid*, Section 83(2)(a)(vi) and (4)(e).

²⁰⁵ *Ibid*, Section 83(2)(a).

- (viii) Where the court finds that: (a) the subject matter of the dispute is not capable of settlement by arbitration under any written laws of Mainland Tanzania;²⁰⁶ or (b) the recognition or enforcement of the arbitral award would be contrary to any written laws, norms, or public policy of Mainland Tanzania.²⁰⁷

10. TIMEFRAME FOR RECOGNITION AND ENFORCING ARBITRAL AWARDS IN MAINLAND TANZANIA

As considered below, arbitral awards should be enforced within a prescribed timeframe; otherwise, the court will refuse to recognise and enforce arbitral awards filed out of the prescribed time. However, where a defaulting party has sufficient cause for the delay to enforce the award within the prescribed timeframe, it may apply to the court with competent jurisdiction for extension of time.

10.1 Time limit for filing an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement in Mainland Tanzania

As in all judicial proceedings, the filing of arbitral awards in court for recognition and enforcement is limited by the law of limitation. In Mainland Tanzania, setting a time limit for filing an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement is crucial for ensuring the finality of arbitral proceedings and promoting legal certainty. This limitation period helps to prevent indefinite challenges to arbitral awards and encourages parties to act promptly in seeking court intervention in relation to the enforcement of such awards when necessary. For that matter, the laws that recognise arbitral awards in Mainland Tanzania set out specific, distinct timeframes within which a party is allowed to file an arbitral award for recognition and enforcement as canvassed below.

10.2 Different timeframes for filing for recognition of several types of arbitral awards

As the court held in *Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Sec. School*,²⁰⁸ there are 'several types or categories of arbitration awards under different laws and each with its own distinct procedures for enforcement' and the timeframe for doing so.²⁰⁹ Firstly, arbitral awards rendered in suits under the Arbitration Rules (1968) contained in the Second Schedule to the CPC have their own procedure for challenging as well as enforcement of arbitral awards. In particular, the timeframe for filing recognition and enforcement actions in respect of these arbitral awards is set out in Item 18 of Part III of the Schedule to the CPC, which is within six (06) months.²¹⁰

²⁰⁶ Ibid, Section 83(2)(b)(i) and (5)(a).

²⁰⁷ Ibid, Section 83(2)(b)(ii) and (5)(b). For a comprehensive judicial reasoning on public policy as a ground of refusal to recognize an arbitral award in Mainland Tanzania, see particularly *United Republic of Tanzania v. Sunlodges BVI & Sunlodges Tanzania Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Civil Cause No. 373B/2020 (Unreported) ('*Tanzania v. Sunlodges*'); and *Catic International Engineering (T) Ltd. v. University of Dar es Salaam*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Commercial Case No. 1 of 2020 (Unreported) ('*Catic v. UDSM*').

²⁰⁸ *Lukumbulu v. St. Anthony Sec. School*, op. cit.

²⁰⁹ Ibid, p. 21.

²¹⁰ Ibid. See particularly the Law of Limitation Act, Cap. 89 R.E. 2002, Part III of the Schedule (item 18). See also *Kigoma/Ujiji Municipal Council v. Nyakirang'ani Construction Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Commercial Cause No. 239 of 2015 (unreported) ('*Kigoma/Ujiji MC v. Nyakirang'ani*'); *Siemens Ltd. & Another v. Mtibwa Sugar Estate*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc Commercial Cause No. 247 of 2015 (Unreported) ('*Siemens v. Mtibwa Sugar*'); and *Bogeta*

Secondly, arbitral awards made under the Arbitration Act (2020) have their procedure of enforcement and challenge, which is provided for in the Arbitration Act and the Arbitration Regulations (2021). Although the Arbitration Act and the Arbitration Regulations do not set out the time limit for filing arbitral awards in court for recognition and enforcement, such *lacunae* is filled up by the Law of Limitation Act²¹¹ in terms of Sections 17 and 18 thereof. Under Item 21 of Part III of the Schedule to the Law of Limitation Act, the time limit for filing and registration in court for recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards is within sixty (60) days from the date the award in question was rendered.²¹²

Thirdly, foreign arbitral awards that emanate from foreign countries with which Tanzania has no reciprocal treaty arrangement are enforced in court within the time limit of six years in terms of Item 9 of Part I of the Schedule to the Law of Limitation Act.²¹³ Notably, those arbitral awards can be enforced in Mainland Tanzania by way of either an action²¹⁴ or under the provisions of Regulation 66(1) of the Arbitration Regulations (2021) in terms of Sections 73, 83 and 94 of the Arbitration Act²¹⁵ ‘in the same way foreign judgments from foreign countries with which Tanzania has no reciprocal treaty arrangement for direct enforcement of their judgments under the provisions of Reciprocal Enforcement of Foreign Judgments Act, Cap. 8 of the Laws of Tanzania, are enforced by way of an action.’²¹⁶

Engineering Ltd. v. Nanyumbu District Council, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Commercial Cause No. 9 of 2019 (Unreported) (*Bogeta v. Nanyumbu DC*). In *Louis Dreyfus Suisse SA v. Kahama Oil Mills Ltd.* (Commercial Cause No. 67 of 2023) [2024] TZHCComD 105 (7 June 2024) (*Louis Dreyfus v. KOM*), the court observed, at p. 83, that:

‘I hold the view that Item 18 of Part III of the Schedule to the Law of Limitation Act Cap 89 which prescribes 6 months period as the time-frame for filing in Court arbitral awards which are made in arbitration referred without the intervention of a Court, is restricted to arbitral awards emanating from arbitration proceedings regulated by the Arbitration Rules of Procedure under the Second Schedule to the Civil Procedure Code, Cap 33. It does not cover applications for recognition and enforcement of domestic and or foreign arbitral awards in Courts in Tanzania where the applicable law is the Arbitration Act, 2020.’

²¹¹ Law of Limitation Act (Cap. 89 R.E. 2002).

²¹² *Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Sec. School*, op. cit, pp. 22-23. In *Tanzania Cotton Marketing Board v. Cogecot Cotton Company SA*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Civil Appeal No.60 of 1998 (Unreported) (*TCMB v. Cogecot*), the Court of Appeal held that:

‘Applications under the [Arbitration] Ordinance fall under Item 21 of Part III of the First Schedule to the Law of Limitation Act, since the Ordinance itself does not provide for the period of limitation, and the period is 60 days.’ [Emphasis supplied].

²¹³ *Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Sec. School*, ibid, p. 27.

²¹⁴ Ibid (holding that: ‘That is by filing a suit based on the doctrine of obligation.’). See also *Willow Investment v. Mbomba Ntumba & Another* [1996] TLR 377 (HC) (*Willow v. Ntumba*).

²¹⁵ Regulation 66(1) of the Arbitration Rules of Procedures (G.N. No. 146 of 2021) provides for two options to enforce a foreign arbitral award thus:

‘A foreign award shall, subject to the provisions of the Act, be enforceable in the High Court either by action or under the provisions of sections 73, 83 and 94 of the [Arbitration] Act.’

²¹⁶ *Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Sec. School*, op. cit, pp. 29-30 (reasoning that; item 9 of Part I of the Schedule to the Law of Limitation Act is ‘intended to set time limit for filing an action or suit for enforcement of a foreign arbitral award which could not be directly enforced in Tanzania. That is, a foreign arbitral award emanating from a foreign state with which Tanzania has no bilateral or multilateral treaty obligation for making direct recognition and enforcement of its Arbitral Awards. Item 9 of Part I of the Schedule to the Law of Limitation Act, therefore, does not apply to direct enforcement of foreign arbitral awards under the provisions of the Arbitration Act CAP 15, 2020. It does not also apply to domestic arbitral

As the court held in *Lukumbulu Investment v. St. Anthony Sec. School*, the categorization between arbitral awards made in suits rendered under and regulated by the Arbitration Rules (1968) and those rendered under or regulated by the Arbitration Act (2020) and their differential treatment, is relevant in ensuring that parties to arbitral awards abide by the time limit set in these different legislative settings.²¹⁷ Therefore, an award-creditor is required to be mindful of the foregoing time limits for filing an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement, lest they would be time-barred to realize their awards in courts of law in Mainland Tanzania.

10.3 The legal consequence of delay in filing an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement

Both in principle and practice, the legal consequence of delay in filing an arbitral award in court for recognition and enforcement (without leave of the court) ‘is dismissal of the same.’²¹⁸ This position is derived from Section 3 of the Law of Limitation Act, which provides that an application or matter filed in court out of the time prescribed in the Schedule to this law has to be dismissed, whether or not limitation has been set up as a defence. Notably, courts in Tanzania have taken a very strict stance to the question of complying with time limits set out by the law. For example, in *Martin v. KMC*,²¹⁹ it was held that: ‘However unfortunate it may be for the petitioners, the Law of Limitation on actions knows no sympathy or equity. It is a merciless sword that cuts across and deep into those who get caught in its web.’ However, the law of limitation contains an exception to this general rule whereby a defaulting party may, upon exhibiting sufficient cause, apply for extension of time, as considered below.

10.4 Extension of time to enforce an arbitral award out of time

Although an arbitral award must be filed within the prescribed time, where an application for enforcement of an arbitral award is not made within the prescribed time limit, leave of the court should be sought for extension of time to file it out of time.²²⁰ The court’s decision as to whether or not to grant time within which an applicant should to file an arbitral award in court out of time (having failed to do so within the prescribed time) is a decision arrived at as a result of an exercise of the court’s judicial discretion; and not as of right.²²¹ The exercise of this judicial discretion enjoins the court to consider ‘all relevant factors’ including ‘the length of delay, the reason for the delay, whether there is an arguable case [in the main application for the matter being pursued] and the degree of prejudice to the defendant if time is extended.’²²²

It has been held in several cases that such discretionary power must be exercised judiciously and it is dependent upon various circumstances, including the need to do

awards of any kind in Tanzania whether under the Arbitration Act or under the provisions of the 2nd Schedule to the Civil Procedure Code.’).

²¹⁷ Ibid, p. 23.

²¹⁸ per Philip, J., in *Bogeta v. Nanyumbu DC*, op. cit.

²¹⁹ *Mathew Martin v. Managing Director, Kahama Mining Corporation*, High Court of Tanzania, Civil Case No. 79 of 2006 (Unreported) (*Martin v. KMC*).

²²⁰ Section 14 of the Law of Limitations Act.

²²¹ *Claus Bremer v. Chief Court Administrator*, op. cit.

²²² *Mbogo v. Shah* [1968] EA 93.

substantial justice to the parties to the suit, the nature and reasons for such a delay;²²³ technical delay;²²⁴ and in accordance with sound and reasonable judicial principles.²²⁵ In an application for extension time to file an award out of time, the court is enjoined to consider the issue whether or not the applicant has demonstrated good grounds to warrant it to extend time within which the applicant can file an arbitral award out of time.²²⁶ Therefore, an applicant seeking for extension of time to do a legal act which ought to have been done within a particular prescribed time must account for each day of the delay.²²⁷

It should be noted that; where the arbitrator delays to file an award in court for registration within the prescribed time frame, the award-creditor may invoke such delay as sufficient cause for applying for extension of time to file the award out of time.²²⁸ Where a point of law at issue is the illegality or otherwise of the decision being challenged, that by itself constitutes 'sufficient reason' for extension of time.²²⁹ Nevertheless, where illegality is put forward as a ground for extension of time, the applicant must substantiate the illegality in terms of lack of jurisdiction on the part of the court; that the case was barred under some law of limitation or that there was a denial of the right to be heard.²³⁰ However, financial constraint is not a sufficient ground for extension of time to file an arbitral award out of time.²³¹

11. CONCLUSION

Universally, arbitration is a consent-based dispute resolution mechanism whereby parties do consensually agree in an arbitration clause to resort to arbitration and to be bound by the decision of the arbitral tribunal. This view implies that; once an arbitral award is

²²³ See, for example, *Lyamuya Construction Co. Ltd. v. Board of Registered Trustees of Young Women's Christian Association of Tanzania*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Civil Appl. No. 2/2010 (Unreported) ('*Lyamuya Construction v. YWCA-T*').

²²⁴ *Bharya Engineering and Contracting Co. Ltd. (BECCO) v. The Arab Contractors and Osman Ahmed Osman & Co. Ltd. & Elsewedy Electric Co. Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division), Misc. Commercial Application No. 165 of 2023 (Unreported) ('*Bharya Engineering v. Arab Contractors*'). See also *Fortunata Masha v. William Shija & Another* [1997] TLR 154 ('*Masha v. Shija*').

²²⁵ See particularly *Rookey's Case* 77ER 209; (1597) 5 Co.Rep.99js; and *Osborn v. Bank of the United States*, 22 U. S. 738 1824j.).

²²⁶ Section 14(1) of the Law of Limitation Act, Cap. 89 R.E. 2002. See also *Lyamuya Construction v. YWCA-T*, op. cit.

²²⁷ *Hassan Bushiri v. Latifa Lukio Mashayo*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania, Civil Application No. 3/2007 (Unreported) ('*Bushiri v. Mashayo*').

²²⁸ *Lazafa v. WVT*, op. cit.

²²⁹ See particularly *VIP Engineering and Marketing Ltd. & 2 Others v. Citibank Tanzania Ltd.*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Civil References Nos. 6, 7 & 8 of 2006 (Unreported) ('*VIP Engineering v. Citibank-T*').

²³⁰ See, for instance, *Tanganyika Wattle Co. Ltd. v. Dolphin Bay Chemicals (Pty) Ltd.*, High Court of Tanzania (Commercial Division) at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Commercial Cause No. 104 of 2023 (Arising from Misc. Commercial Cause No. 17 of 2019) (Unreported) ('*Tanganyika Wattle v. Dolphin Bay Chemicals*'); and *Charles Richard Kombe v. Kinondoni Municipal Council*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Civil Reference No. 13/2019 (Unreported) ('*Kombe v. KMC*'); and *William Mpalange v. Lilian Bavu*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Misc. Civil Application No.501/2020 (Unreported) ('*Mpalange v. Bavu*').

²³¹ *Wambele Mtimwa Shahame v. Mohamed Hamis*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Civil Ref. No. 8/2016 (Unreported) ('*Shahame v. Hamis*'); *Yusufu Same & Another v. Hadija Yusufu*, Court of Appeal of Tanzania at Dar es Salaam, Civil Appeal No. 1/2002 (Unreported) ('*Same v. Yusufu*'); and *Zabitis Kawuka v. Abdul Karim* (EACA) Civil Appeal No. A8/1937) ('*Kawuka v. Karim*').

rendered by the arbitral tribunal, an award-debtor should immediately honour it in order to signify that party's honest respect for the sacrosanct autonomy to consensually agree to go to arbitration. However, where the award-debtor does not voluntarily and immediately honour the arbitral award, the award-creditor is at liberty to commence recognition and enforcement proceedings in the court of competent jurisdiction.²³²

As considered above, both under the repealed and the current arbitration legal regimes in Mainland Tanzania, there have been uncertainties as to what is the proper procedure for filing in court arbitral awards for recognition and enforcement. However, the article has found that the current arbitration legislation, practice and caselaw have rectified this anomaly and now the procedure is clearly spelt out in the following sequence: a party should file the arbitral award in court for registration, the court should issue notice to the parties to show course why the award should not be recognised and subsequently enforced, and when the parties appear in court: (i) when they do not contest, the award should be recognised and enforced as a decree of the court, and (ii) where a party wants to challenge the award, such a party will have to file a petition for challenging the same and the court would stay the proceedings recognition and enforcement of the award pending the outcome of the petition for challenging the award.

As observed above, matters for recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards must be filed within the timeframe set out in the relevant law, otherwise the court will dismiss such application for being time-barred. Nevertheless, there are certain exceptional circumstances, as canvassed in this article, where an application for recognition and enforcement of an arbitral award may be entertained and granted by the court but only in its judicial discretion.²³³ Therefore, it is urged that award-creditors should be mindful of both the procedural prerequisites and time-frame for filing applications for recognition and enforcement of arbitral award, lest the same would be held incompetent and thereby prejudicing their right to realize the fruits of their respective arbitral awards.

²³² *Patel v. Patel*, op. cit.

²³³ See, for instance, *Mbogo v. Shah*, op. cit; *Lyamuya Construction. v. YWCA-T*, op. cit; *Claus Bremer v. Chief Court Administrator*, op. cit; and *Bharya Engineering v. Arab Contractors*, op. cit.